

THE
ARANEIDAE
OF
SOUTH AFRICA
Part 2 E-N

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GENUS *ERIOVIXIA* Archer, 1951

The genus *Eriovixia* described by Archer (1951) is known from 22 species but only three species are reported from Africa (World Spider Catalog 2020) of which one has recently been recorded from South Africa (Dippenaar-Schoeman 2014; Dippenaar-Schoeman et al. 2021) and Swaziland for the first time.

COMMON NAMES: Eriovixia Araneid Spiders

TYPE SPECIES: *Eriovixia rhinura* (Pocock, 1900)

MORPHOLOGY: They are small spiders with a total length of 3-6 mm. The carapace as wide as long; cephalic region raised bearing dense setae; eyes on tubercles is more distinct in males. The abdomen is almost round, save for the pronounced easily visible tail like extension. It varies from small humps to pointed extensions, usually brownish grey to dark brown; hairy. Ventrally abdomen with yellow spots. In males the abdomen is decorated with setae and white spots. Legs are short and grouped together around the carapace. In males legs with long spines (Dippenaar-Schoeman 2014; Dippenaar-Schoeman et al. 2021).

LIFE STYLE: They make orb-webs between vegetation. The bridge line usually very long.

TAXONOMY: African species not yet revised.

Eriovixia excelsa female from Dinokeng Photos P. Webb

Eriovixia excelsa male from Bergpan Photos P. Webb

Eriovixia excelsa (Simon, 1889)

COMMON NAME: Hump back Araneid Spider / Tailed Araneid Spider

CONSERVATION STATUS: LC

NATIONAL RATIONALE: A species described by Simon (1889) as *Glyptogona excelsa*. The species has a wide global distribution. It has recently been recorded from South Africa and Swaziland for the first time. In South Africa recorded from four provinces. (EOO= 53 505 km²; AOO= 36 km²; 148-1444 m a.s.l.). Due to its wide geographical range, it is listed Least Concern.

LIFE STYLE: They make orb-webs between vegetation usually with a very long bridge line. The species was sampled from the Grassland and Savanna biomes. Heron (2016) observed a mimetic relationship between the beetle *Cassida calvaria* and *Eriovixia excelsa* in the Palmiet Nature Reserve at Westville near Durban in October 2010. They were of similar size, colouring and body patterns (Dippenaar-Schoeman 2014; Heron 2016).

GLOBAL DISTRIBUTION: India, Pakistan, China, Taiwan, Philippines, Indonesia, and Africa: Swaziland and South Africa.

DISTRIBUTION SOUTH AFRICA: **Gauteng:** Roodeplaatdam Nature Reserve (-25.64, 28.36); Roodeplaat Research Station (-25.66, 28.35); Irene Veld (field opposite Gem Village) (-25.89, 28.23); Ezemvelo Nature Reserve (-25.80, 28.77). **Mpumalanga:** Nelspruit (-25.34, 31.77); Loskopdam, Farm Ranch 2D (-25.43, 29.33). **North West:** Mooi Nooi (-25.75, 27.57). **KwaZulu-Natal:** Ndumo Game Reserve (-27.33, 31.45).

CONSERVATION MEASURES: Protected in the following areas: Roodeplaatdam Nature Reserve, Ezemvelo Nature Reserve and Ndumo Game Reserve. No conservation actions are recommended.

TAXONOMIC NOTES: Species known from both sexes.

Eriovixia excelsa female Klein Kariba Photo P. Webb

Eriovixia excelsa male in web Photo P. Webb

Eriovixia excelsa female Ezemvelo Photo P. Webb

After Archer (1951)

GENUS *GASTERACANTHA* Sundevall, 1833

The genus *Gasteracantha* Sundevall, 1833 is represented by 101 species and subspecies (World Spider Catalog 2020). Four species are known from South Africa.

COMMON NAMES: Kite spiders

TYPE SPECIES: *Gasteracantha cancriformis* (Linnaeus, 1758)

MORPHOLOGY: Kite spiders are brightly coloured with striking patterns. The carapace is usually as broad as it is long. The spiders have hard, shell-like flattened bodies. The abdomen is wider than long. Dorsally the spiders are decorated with modified spines that differ in length and shape between the species. Also dorsally the abdomen has a number of small elongate sigilla, usually dark-coloured. The male's abdomen is without spines. The venter of the abdomen has a bulge. Variation in colour and shape occur between the species. The immature spiders differ from the adults in colour (Dippenaar-Schoeman 2014).

LIFE STYLE: The web of gasteracanthines is a complete orb, made either vertically or on an inclined plane, with an open hub, many radii and viscid spirals. A distinct feature is the occurrence of series of flocculent tufts of silk attached either to the radii or to the bridge and foundation lines (Nentwig & Heimer, 1987). The tufts consist of a mass of thin threads. The spider hangs in the middle of the web in the open hub. The web is made between trees and shrubs, occasionally high up between branches in tall trees. Although several papers have been published on their taxonomy and distribution, very little is known about the natural history of the Afrotropical species (Dippenaar-Schoeman & Jocqué 1997) The orb-webs are usually made high in trees or tall shrubs above the observer's eye level. The bridge line is frequently longer than the orb part. It gives the impression that the spider is floating in space. The spiders are active during the day and do not remove their webs (Dippenaar-Schoeman & Van den Berg 2010; Dippenaar-Schoeman & Haddad 2013).

TAXONOMY: No recent revisions

Gasteracantha milvoides female Photo J. van Zyl

Gasteracantha versicolor female Photo Koos Geldenhuys

Gasteracantha versicolor female in web Photo Allen Jones

Gasteracantha falcicornis Butler, 1873

COMMON NAME: Long Wing Kite Spider

CONSERVATION STATUS: LC

NATIONAL RATIONALE: An African endemic described by Butler (1873). The species is recorded from five African countries. In South Africa the species is known from two provinces (EEO=43523 km²; AOO=40 km²; 4-750 m a.s.l.). Due to its wide geographical range the species is listed as Least Concern.

LIFE STYLE: Orb-web dweller. The webs are usually made high in trees or tall shrubs above the observer's eye level. The bridge line is frequently longer than the orb part. It gives the impression that the spider is floating in space. The web is sometimes decorated with tufts of silk. The spiders are active during the day and do not remove their webs. Sampled from two biomes (Foord et al. 2011).

GLOBAL DISTRIBUTION: Malawi, Tanzania, Zambia, Swaziland and South Africa.

DISTRIBUTION SOUTH AFRICA: *KwaZulu-Natal:* Empangeni (-28.72, 31.88); iSimangaliso Wetland Park: Fanie's Island (-28.1, 32.45), Kosi Bay Nature Reserve (-26.93, 32.87), Sodwana Bay National Park (-27.4, 32.76), Lake Sibaya (-27.35, 32.7); Jozini (-27.42, 32.07); Ngoye Forest (-28.88,31.38); Tembe Elephant Park (-26.94, 32.47). *Mpumalanga:* Avoca (-25.68, 31.17); Komatipoort (-25.43, 31.94).

CONSERVATION MEASURES: Protected in the following areas: Kosi Bay Nature Reserve, Ngoye Forest and Tembe Elephant Park. No conservation actions are recommended.

TAXONOMIC NOTES: Last revised by Emerit (1974). Known from the female.

Gasteracantha falcicornis female from Sodwana Bay Photo Astri Leroy

Gasteracantha falcicornis female in web Photo K. Braun

Habitus after Emerit (1974)

Gasteracantha falcicornis female from Swaziland Photo K. Braun

Gasteracantha milvoidea Butler, 1873

COMMON NAME: Medium Wing Kite Spider

CONSERVATION STATUS: LC

NATIONAL RATIONALE: An African endemic described by Butler (1873) from South Africa (no exact locality). Known from six African countries. In South Africa the species is known from four provinces (EOO= 325 208 km²; AOO= 108 km²; 5-1341 m a.s.l.). Due to its wide geographical range, it is listed as Least Concern.

LIFE STYLE: Orb-web dweller. A species commonly found in the warmer tropical regions. The orb-webs are usually made in trees or tall shrubs, from waist height to above the observer's eye level. The bridge line is frequently longer than the orb part. It gives the impression that the spider is floating in space. The web is sometimes decorated with tufts of silk. The spiders are active during the day and do not remove their webs. Sampled from the Forest, Indian Coastal Belt, Grassland (Haddad et al. 2013), Savanna and Thicket biomes (Foord et al. 2011).

GLOBAL DISTRIBUTION: Central African Republic, Kenya, Namibia, Zimbabwe, Swaziland and South Africa.

DISTRIBUTION SOUTH AFRICA. Eastern Cape: Fish River (-33.6, 26.85). **KwaZulu-Natal:** Dukuduku Forest Station (-28.37, 32.23); Empangeni (-28.72, 31.88); Enseleni Nature Reserve (-28.68, 32.05); Entumeni Nature Reserve (-28.88, 31.29); Eshowe (-28.89, 31.47); Hluhluwe Nature Reserve (-28.09, 32.1); iSimangaliso Wetland Parks: Cape Vidal (-28.16, 32.56), Kosi Bay Nature Reserve (-26.93, 32.87), Mkuzi Game Reserve (-27.63, 32.25), Sodwana Bay National Park (-27.4, 32.76), St. Lucia (-28.36, 32.41); Ndumo Game Reserve (-26.87, 32.24); Ngome State Forest (-27.78, 31.45); Nyalu Game Reserve (-28.72, 31.88); Oribi Gorge Nature Reserve (-30.71, 30.26); Pongola (Farm Vergeval) (-27.35, 31.61); Richards Bay (15 km N) (-28.78, 32.1); Tembe Elephant Park (-26.94, 32.47); Valley Bush (-28, 32); Vernon Crookes Nature Reserve (-30.27, 30.57). **Limpopo:** Kruger National Park (-22.93, 31.02); Lhuvhondo Nature Reserve (-23.03, 29.45); Ratombo Forest (-23.06, 30.17); Lekgalameetse Nature Reserve (-23.82, 30.16); **Mpumalanga:** Malelane (-25.49, 31.5); Burgers Hall (-25.08, 31.06).

CONSERVATION MEASURES: Protected in >18 protected areas such as Ndumo Game Reserve (Haddad et al. 2006); Kruger National Park (Dippenaar-Schoeman & Leroy 2003) and Lekgalameetse Nature Reserve (Foord et al. 2016). No conservation actions are recommended.

TAXONOMIC NOTES: Last revised by Emerit (1973). Known from both sexes.

Gasteracantha milvoidea female from Sandkraal Photo J. van Zyl

Gasteracantha milvoidea female from Nelspruit Photo A. Louw

Gasteracantha milvoidea female from Opathe NR Photo Ernst Klimsa

Gasteracantha milvoidea female Photo P. Webb

After Emerit (1973).

Gasteracantha sanguinolenta C. L. Koch, 1844

COMMON NAME: Short-Wing Kite Spider

CONSERVATION STATUS: LC

NATIONAL RATIONALE: An African endemic described by C. L. Koch (1844) from South Africa with type locality only Cap der guten Hoffnung. The species is known from several countries throughout Africa. In South Africa it is known from eight of the nine provinces including nine protected areas (EEO= 759 576 km²; AOO=116 km²; 6-1 556m a.s.l.). Due to its wide global distribution, it is listed as being of Least Concern.

LIFE STYLE: Orb-web dweller. A species commonly found in the warmer tropical regions.. The orb-web are usually made high in trees or tall shrubs above the observer's eye level. The bridge line is frequently longer than the orb part. It gives the impression that the spider is floating in space. The web is sometimes decorated with tufts of silk. The spiders are active during the day and do not remove their webs (Dippenaar-Schoeman 2014). Sampled from all the floral biomes except from the Nama and Succulent Karoo biomes (Haddad et al. 2013), Foord et al. 2011).

GLOBAL DISTRIBUTION: Known throughout Africa, São Tomé, Yemen, Seychelles, Socotra, Swaziland and South Africa.

DISTRIBUTION SOUTH AFRICA: **Eastern Cape:** Addo Elephant National Park (-33.32, 25.72); Baviaanskloof Nature Reserve (-33.76, 24.81); Cintsa (-32.83, 28.06); Grahamstown (Kowa) (-33.3, 26.52). **Free State:** Bloemfontein (-29.11, 26.22). **Gauteng:** Roodeplaatdam Nature Reserve (-25.64, 28.36). **KwaZulu-Natal:** Durban (-29.85, 31.01); Glen Bush, Richmond (-29.86, 30.26); Noodsberg (-29.37, 30.73); Pietermaritzburg (-29.6, 30.38); Port Edward (-31.04, 30.21); Ubombo (-27.56, 32.08). **Limpopo:** Alma (-24.49, 28.07); Kampersrus (-24.48, 30.83); Lhuvhondo Nature Reserve (-23.03, 29.45); Polokwane Nature Reserve (-23.9, 29.47); Springbok Flats (Tuinplaas) (-24.9, 28.73); Roodewal Forest (-23.02, 30.03); Lekgalameetse Nature Reserve (-23.82, 30.16); Kruger National Park (-22.93, 31.02). **Mpumalanga:** Barberton (-25.79, 31.04); Goedehoop Forest (-25.02, 30.39); Wagon Drift (-25.11, 30.49). **North West:** Brits (-25.62, 27.77). **Western Cape:** Bergvliet (-34.03, 18.63); Hangklip, Pringle Bay (-34.34, 18.83); Table Mountain National Park (-33.82, 18.48).

CONSERVATION MEASURES: Protected in >10 protected areas such as Lhuvhondo Nature Reserve (Foord et al. 2002); Kruger National Park (Dippenaar-Schoeman & Leroy 2003); Polokwane Nature Reserve (Dippenaar et al. 2008) and Lekgalameetse Nature Reserve (Foord et al. 2016). No conservation actions are recommended.

TAXONOMIC NOTES: Last revised by Emerit (1974). Known from both sexes.

Gasteracantha sanguinolenta female from Mooi Nooi
Photo Peter Webb

Gasteracantha sanguinolenta female from
Legalameetse NR Photo Peter Webb

Gasteracantha sanguinolenta female from Montagu
Photo W. Jubber

After Koch (1844)

Gasteracantha versicolor (Walckenaer, 1842)

COMMON NAME: Common Kite Spider

CONSERVATION STATUS: LC

NATIONAL RATIONALE: An African endemic described by Walckenaer (1842) as *Plectana versicolor*. Known from several countries throughout Africa. In South Africa the species is known from six provinces (EOO=790 063 km²; AOO=156 km²; 7-1710 m a.s.l.). Due to its wide geographical distribution, it is listed as Least Concern.

LIFE STYLE: Orb-web dweller. A species commonly found in the warmer tropical regions. They usually make their orb-webs high between trees or tall shrubs above the observer's eye level. The bridge line is frequently longer than the orb part. It gives the impression that the spider is floating in space. The web is sometimes decorated with tufts of silk. The spiders are active during the day and do not remove their webs. Sampled from the Fynbos, Forest, Grassland and Savanna biomes (Haddad et al. 2013; Foord et al. 2011). The species was also sampled from citrus orchards (Dippenaar-Schoeman et al. 2013).

GLOBAL DISTRIBUTION: Widespread throughout Africa. Sampled from Swaziland and South Africa.

DISTRIBUTION SOUTH AFRICA: **Eastern Cape:** East London (-33.01, 27.9); Coffee Bay (-31.97, 29.14); Grahamstown Dassie Krantz (-33.3, 26.52); King William's Town Pirie Forest (-32.88, 27.39); Port Alfred (-33.58, 26.89); Port Elizabeth (-33.95, 25.61); Port St. Johns (-31.63, 29.53). **Gauteng:** Bronkhorstspuit Tiegervoort (-25.8, 28.74); Pretoria/Tshwane Wonderboom-South (-25.74, 28.19); Randfontein (-26.17, 27.7). **KwaZulu-Natal:** Durban (-29.85, 31.01); iSimangaliso Wetland Park: Kosi Bay Nature Reserve (-26.93, 32.87); Port Shepstone (-30.74, 30.44); Umtamvuna Nature Reserve (-31.06, 30.17); Greytown (-29.05, 30.6); Ngome State Forest (-27.78, 31.45); Nyala Game Reserve (-28.72, 31.88); Pongola, Farm Vergeval, district Ngotsche (-27.35, 31.61); Sungulwane Game Reserve (-28.87, 31.18); Hluhluwe Nature Reserve (-28.09, 32.10). **Limpopo:** Kruger National Park (-22.93, 31.02); Dendron, Farm Amsterdam (-23.37, 29.32); Haenertsburg (-23.94, 29.95); Hoedspruit Hippo Pools (-24.34, 30.93); Leggalameetse Nature Reserve, Farm Malta (-24.17, 30.25); Levubu (-23.08, 30.28); Makgokolo Game Reserve (-24.17, 30.52); Mara Mara (-23.04, 29.66); Mosdene Nature Reserve Naboomspruit. (-24.52, 28.7); New Agatha Forest (-24.03, 30.08); Swadini Nature Reserve Swadinil, Blyde River Resort (-24.34, 30.93); Tzaneen (-23.82, 30.16); Westphalia (-23.3, 29.18); Wolkberg Nature Reserve Haenertsburg (-23.94, 29.95).

Gasteracantha versicolor female from Dullstroom Photo P. Webb

Gasteracantha versicolor female
Photo Koos Geldenhuys

Gasteracantha versicolor female from Kampferust
Photo P. Webb

Gasteracantha versicolor female ventral
View Photo Peter Webb

After Emerit (1973)

Gasteracantha versicolor (continued)

Mpumalanga: Mariepskop (-24.58, 30.87); Nelspruit (-25.47, 30.96); Bergvliet Forest Station (-25.1, 30.78); Burgers Hall (-25.76, 31.6); Buffelspruit, Farm Amo (-25.63, 31.47); Lydenburg. (-25.09, 30.46). **Western Cape:** Table Mountain National Park: Newlands Forest (-33.91, 18.42).

CONSERVATION MEASURES: Protected in >10 protected areas such as Kruger National Park (Dippenaar-Schoeman & Leroy 2003); Lekgalameetse Nature Reserve (Foord et al. 2016) and Table Mountain National Park. No conservation actions are recommended.

TAXONOMIC NOTES: Known from both sexes (Emerit 1973, 1974).

Gasteracantha versicolor female from Hluhluwe Nature Reserve Photo Ernst Klimsa

Gasteracantha versicolor female Photo Les Oates

GENUS GASTROXYA Benoit, 1962

An African endemic genus described by Benoit (1962) and known from four species (World Spider Catalog 2020) Only *Gastroxya benoiti* is known from South Africa

COMMON NAMES: Spotted Kite Spiders

TYPE SPECIES: *Gastroxya schoutedeni* Benoit, 1962

MORPHOLOGY: Carapace wider than long covered by white setae; fovea longitudinal; eyes in two rows; lateral eyes closely spaced near lateral edge; cheliceral furrow with two rows of teeth; sternum with curved tip. Dorsum of abdomen with a double row of 18 marginal sigilla; four sigilla form a trapezoid medially with double row on posterior border; ventrally without protuberances. Epigyne a longitudinal crest flanked by two deep round indentations. Femur of male palp with strong tooth at base.

LIFE STYLE: Nothing is known about their behaviour.

TAXONOMY: Genus not revised.

Gastroxya benoiti Photo Nicky Bay

Gastroxya benoiti Emerit, 1973

COMMON NAME: Benoit's Spotted Kite Spider

CONSERVATION STATUS: DDT

NATIONAL RATIONALE: A South African endemic species described in 1973 as *Gastroxya benoiti* from Port St Johns. The species has a restricted distribution and is present only known from two specimens sampled in the Eastern Cape and KwaZulu-Natal. The species is rare and under collected. Some more sampling is needed to collect the male and to determine the species' range. Therefore listed as Data Deficient for Taxonomic reasons.

LIFE STYLE: Not known.

GLOBAL DISTRIBUTION: South Africa.

DISTRIBUTION SOUTH AFRICA: *KwaZulu-Natal:* Durban (-29.85, 31.01). *Eastern Cape:* Port St. Johns, Mouth of the Umgazi (-31.63, 29.53).

CONSERVATION MEASURES:

Some more sampling is needed to collect the male and to determine the species' range.

TAXONOMIC NOTES: Not revised.

After Emerit (1973)

After Emerit (1973)

Gastroxya benoiti Photo Nicky Bay

GENUS *GEA* C. L. Koch, 1843

The genus *Gea* C.L. Koch, 1843 is known from 12 species with four species recorded from Africa (World Spider Catalog 2020).

COMMON NAMES: Gea Orb-Web Spiders

TYPE SPECIES: *Gea spinipes* C.L. Koch, 1843

MORPHOLOGY: Size: TL female 4-6 mm, male 3-4.5 mm. *Gea* differs from *Argiope* in having the anterior eyes evenly spaced. It differs from most araneid genera by having the posterior eye row strongly procurved and a low thoracic region of the carapace. *Gea* specimens are smaller than *Argiope* and have larger posterior median eyes. In the females the eyes of the posterior eye row are almost equally spaced, whereas in *Argiope*, the median eyes are closer to each other than to the laterals. Abdomen shield shaped with lobes on sides; color of the abdomen is variable; there may be transverse lines or a dark folium. Another character that separates *Gea* from other genera is the modified first tibia of the male that is curved and armed with macro-setae.

LIFE STYLE: According to Simon (1895), they do not make a stabilimentum but it has been observed in webs of some webs.

TAXONOMY: African species not revised.

Gea infuscata female

Photo Jason Boyce

Gea infusata Tullgren, 1910

COMMON NAME: Gea Orb-Web Spider

CONSERVATION STATUS: LC

NATIONAL RATIONALE: An African endemic described by Tullgren (1910) from Tanzania. The species is known from five African countries. However it is possibly under collected and is suspected to occur in more countries in-between. In South Africa, it is known from five provinces (EOO= 641 980km²; AOO=72km²; 1-1323 m a.s.l.). Due to its wide geographical distribution, it is listed as Least Concern.

LIFE STYLE: The spider makes an orb-web with a round zigzag stabilimentum, giving it a doily appearance. Sampled from the Fynbos, Forest and Savanna biomes. (Foord et al. 2011).

GLOBAL DISTRIBUTION: Tanzania, Angola, Botswana, Sudan and South Africa.

DISTRIBUTION SOUTH AFRICA: **Eastern Cape:** Jeffrey's Bay (-34.04, 24.94); Kei River Mouth (-32.68, 28.37); Keurkloof (Baviaanskloof) (Farm Ferndale) (-33.68, 24.83); Maz-eppa Bay (-32.47, 28.64); Addo Elephant National Park (-33.32, 25.72); Alexandria (-33.65,26.4); Grahamstown (-33.3, 26.52); Mkhambathi Nature Reserve (-31.32,29.97) **KwaZulu-Natal:** Ndumo Game Reserve (-26.87, 32.24) iSimangaliso Wetland park, Sodwana Bay (-27.4,32.76); iSimangaliso Wetland park, Fanie's Island (-28.1, 32.45); La Mercy (-29.63, 31.13); Ndumo Game Reserve Pongola River (-26.87,32.24); Ngoye Forest (-28.88, 31.38); Alverstone near Hillcrest (-29.77, 30.73); Tembe Elephant Park (-27.0337, 32.4245). **Limpopo:** Polokwane Nature Reserve (-23.9, 29.47); Tshipise, Farm Alicedale (-22.62, 30.14). **Mpumalanga:** Sabi River Banks (-24.98, 31.58). **Western Cape:** Fisherhaven, Hermanus (-34.47, 19.27); Knysna (-34.03,23.03).

CONSERVATION MEASURES: Protected in the following reserves such as Addo Elephant National Park (Dippenaar-Schoeman et al. 2020); Mkhambathi Nature Reserve (Dippenaar-Schoeman et al. 2011); Ndumo Game Reserve (Haddad et al. 2006); Tembe Elephant Park (Haddad et al. 2009) and Polokwane Nature Reserve (Dippenaar et al. 2008). No conservation actions are recommended.

TAXONOMIC NOTES: Not revised. Known from both sexes.

Gea infusata female Photo Hannes Mitchell

Gea infusata female Photo Linda Wiese

Gea infusata female Photo J. Wilkinson

Eye Photo C. Haddad

After Tullgren (1910)

UNDETERMINED SPECIES

GENUS *GEA* (continued)

Gea transversovittata Tullgren, 1910 NOT CONFIRMED FROM SA

Maybe new *Gea* Peter Webb Lekgalameetse NR

Hhulhuwe Game Reserve Ernst Klimsa

Maybe new *Gea* Tembe Elephant Park Duncan MacFyden

Ndumo Len de Beer

Maybe new *Ndumu* GR

Hoedspruit

GENUS *HYP SACANTHA* Dahl, 1914

A monotypic African genus described by Dahl (1914) (World Spider Catalog 2020). It was removed from the synonymy of *Gasteracantha* Sundevall, 1833 by Emerit (1973).

COMMON NAMES: Hypsacantha Kite Spiders

TYPE SPECIES: *Hypsacantha crucimaculata* (Dahl, 1914)

MORPHOLOGY: Size: TL female 6-7 mm, male 3-5 mm. Carapace broad; dark brown clothed with strong white setae; median eyes on small tubercles; lateral eyes near the border of the carapace. Abdomen is hard and leathery; anterior edge is slightly rounded with two small tubercles; six sigilla present at the base of spine II; abdomen slightly slopes to the rear, with two pairs of small tubercles, the medial pair pointing upwards. Legs are short and the same colour as the carapace.

LIFE STYLE: Nothing is known about their behaviour.

TAXONOMY: Last discussed by Emerit (1973). Known from both sexes.

Hypsacantha crucimaculata from Lekgalameetse NR Photo Peter Webb

Hypsacantha crucimaculata from Lekgalameetse NR Photo Peter Webb

Hypsacantha crucimaculata from Bontebok NP Photo E. Klimsa

Hypsacantha crucimaculata (Dahl, 1914)

COMMON NAME: Hypsacantha Kite Spider

CONSERVATION STATUS: LC

NATIONAL RATIONALE: An African endemic described by Dahl (1914) as *Gasterantha crucimaculata* from Tanzania. The species is known from six African countries, but it is possibly under collected and is suspected to occur in more countries in between. In South Africa, the species is known from six provinces (EOO=433 711km²; AOO=40km²; 54 -1513 m a.s.l.). Due to its wide geographical range, the species is listed as Least Concern.

GLOBAL DISTRIBUTION: Central African Republic, Democratic Republic of the Congo, Mozambique, Tanzania Zimbabwe and South Africa

DISTRIBUTION SOUTH AFRICA: **Eastern Cape:** Mountain Zebra National Park (-32.24, 25.43). **KwaZulu-Natal:** iSimangaliso Wetland park, Mkuze Game Reserve (-27.63, 32.25); Ophathe Game Reserve (-28.52, 31.66); Ndumo Game Reserve (-26.544, 32.155); Tembe Elephant Park (-27.0337, 32.4245); Pongola, Farm Vergeval, district Ngotsche (-27.35, 31.61). **Limpopo:** Makalali Nature Reserve (-24.34, 30.93); Lekgalameetse Nature Reserve, Farm Malta (-24.17, 30.25). **Mpumalanga:** Kruger National Park (Skukuza) (-24.99, 31.59). **North West:** Pilanesberg Nature Reserve (-25.25, 27.08). **Western Cape:** Karoo National Park Stalshoek (-32.28, 22.46); Bontebok National Park (-34.07, 20.45).

LIFE STYLE: They make an orb-web but nothing more is known about their behaviour. Sampled from the Nama Karoo and Savanna biomes (Foord et al. 2011).

CONSERVATION MEASURES. There are no known threats to the species. Sampled from the following protected areas such as Ophathe Game Reserve (Haddad & Dippenaar-Schoeman 2015); Makalali Nature Reserve (Whitmore et al. 2002); Karoo National Park (Dippenaar-Schoeman et al. 1999) and Kruger National Park (Dippenaar-Schoeman & Leroy 2003).

TAXONOMIC NOTES: Revised by Emerit (1973). Known from both sexes.

Hypsacantha crucimaculata female after Emerit (1973)

Hypsacantha crucimaculata male
Photo Peter Webb

Hypsacantha crucimaculata from Lekgalameetse NR Photo Peter Webb

GENUS *HYPSSOSINGA* Ausserer, 1871

The genus *Hypsosinga* was described by Ausserer (1871) and it is known from 18 species and three subspecies. Several species have a world-wide distribution of which two presently are known from Africa (World Spider Catalog 2020).

COMMON NAMES: Hypsosinga False Pyjama Spiders

TYPE SPECIES: *Hypsosinga sanguinea* (C. L. Koch, 1844)

MORPHOLOGY: The genera *Singa* and *Hypsosinga* comprise small spiders identifiable by a shiny body decorated with spots or lines. *Hypsosinga* has the carapace smooth and rather wide in front, wider than the eye area; there is no thoracic depression, or sometimes only a small longitudinal black mark in the male; integument shiny; eye area usually black; posterior median eyes usually their own diameter apart. *Hypsosinga* differs from *Singa* in having the posterior median eyes the largest; ocular quadrangle is wider behind than in front, or rectangular. Abdomen in *Hypsosinga* unlike that of *Singa* tends to be oval, widest in the middle, with either two dorsal longitudinal bands or four dark spots. The epigynum differs from those of both *Singa* and *Araneus* in lacking a scape (Dippenaar-Schoeman 2014).

LIFE STYLE: They live on low plants where their small orb-webs frequently go unnoticed. Levy (1984) reported on a species that lives under stones and which could easily be confused with theridiids (especially *Steatoda* spp.). *Hypsosinga* make a complete orb-web usually with a retreat. They are frequently sampled in sweep nets in grassland.

TAXONOMY: African species not revised.

Hypsosinga lithyphantoides female Photo P. Webb

Hypsosinga pygmaea female Photo P. Webb

Hypsosinga sp.? female Photo P. Webb

Hypsosinga sp. female Photo P. Webb

Hypsosinga holzapfelae (Lessert, 1936)

COMMON NAME: Spotted Araneus Hairy Field Spider

CONSERVATION STATUS: LC

NATIONAL RATIONALE: An African endemic described from Mozambique by Lessert (1936). It has since been sampled from three African countries. This species is possibly under collected and is suspected to occur in the countries in-between. In South Africa, the species is known from five provinces (EOO=195 565 km²; AOO=60 km²; 78-1556 m a.s.l.). Due to its wide geographical range the species is listed as Least Concern.

LIFE STYLE: Orb-web spiders making their webs in vegetation. Sampled from the Savanna (Foord et al. 2011) and Thicket biomes. The species was also sampled from macadamia (Dippenaar-Schoeman et al. 2001), avocado orchards (Dippenaar-Schoeman et al. 2005) and tomatoes (Dippenaar-Schoeman et al. 2013).

GLOBAL DISTRIBUTION: Mozambique, Kenya and South Africa.

DISTRIBUTION SOUTH AFRICA: Gauteng: Ezemvelo Nature Reserve (-25.8, 28.77); Faerie Glenn Nature Reserve (-25.74, 28.19); Tswaing Crater Nature Reserve (-25.42, 28.08).

KwaZulu-Natal: Empangeni (-28.72, 31.88); Isandlwane Nature Reserve (-28.359, 30.64); uMkhuze Game Reserve (-27.6217, 32.2454); Tembe Elephant Park (-27.034, 32.425).

Limpopo: Blouberg Nature Reserve (-22.99, 29.04); Gravelotte (-23.95, 30.57); Little Leigh (Western Soutpansberg) (-22.95, 29.87); Makalali Nature Reserve (-24.34, 30.93); Polokwane Nature Reserve (-23.9, 29.47). **Mpumalanga:** Brondal (-25.35, 30.84); Kruger National Park (-25.01, 31.97). **North West:** Rustenburg Nature Reserve (-25.72, 27.18).

CONSERVATION MEASURES: Sampled from 11 protected areas such as Tembe Elephant park (Haddad et al. 2009), Blouberg (Muelwa et al. 2010; Foord et al. 2019), Makalali Nature Reserve (Whitmore et al. 2001) and Kruger National Park (Dippenaar-Schoeman & Leroy 2003). No conservation actions are recommended.

TAXONOMIC NOTES: Not revised. Known from both sexes (Dippenaar-Schoeman & Foord 2020).

H. holzapfelae male Photo P. Webb

Epigyne after Dippenaar-Schoeman & Foord 2020

Hypsosinga holzapfelae female Photo Peter Webb

Hypsosinga lithyphantoides Caporiacco, 1947

COMMON NAME: False Pyjama Spider

CONSERVATION STATUS: LC

NATIONAL RATIONALE: An African endemic described by Caporiacco (1947) from Uganda. It has been recorded from three African countries. From South Africa it has been collected from five provinces (EEO=370 440 km²; AOO=80 km²; 1-1593 m a.s.l.). Because of wide geographical range, the species is listed as Least Concern .

LIFE STYLE: *Hypsosinga* make a complete orb-web sometimes with a retreat. Sampled mainly by sweep-netting grasses and herbs from the Grassland, Indian Ocean Coastal Belt and Savanna biomes (Foord et al. 2011; Haddad et al. 2013). Also sampled from citrus orchards and potato fields (Dippenaar-Schoeman et al. 2013).

GLOBAL DISTRIBUTION: Kenya, Uganda and South Africa.

DISTRIBUTION IN SOUTH AFRICA: **Eastern Cape:** Mkhambathi Nature Reserve (-31.32, 29.97). **Free State:** Amanzi Private Game Reserve (-28.62, 26.68); Bloemfontein Free State National Botanical Garden (-29.11, 26.22); Clocolan, Mpetsane Conservation Estate (-28.92, 27.58); Erfenis Dam Nature Reserve (-28.5, 26.8); Oranjeville (-26.99, 28.2). **KwaZulu-Natal:** iSimangaliso Wetland park, Sodwana Bay National Park (-27.4, 32.76); Ndumo Game Reserve (-26.87, 32.24); Sani Pass (-30.19, 30.24). **Limpopo:** Blouberg Nature Reserve (-22.99, 29.04); Kruger National Park.(-22.93, 31.02); Lhuvhondo Nature Reserve (-23.038,29.442); Lekgalameetse, Farm Balloon (-24.2, 30.34); Little Leigh (Western Soutpansberg) (-22.9485, 29.8696); Nylsvley Nature Reserve (-24.65, 28.67);Pafuri (Waller's Camp) (-22.424, 30.910); Polokwane Nature Reserve (-23.9, 29.47);Venetia, Limpopo Valley Reserve (-22.3204, 29.3235). **Mpumalanga:** Kruger National Park (Skukuza) (-24.99, 31.59).

CONSERVATION MEASURES: No conservation actions are recommended. Protected in >15 protected areas such as: Mkhambathi Nature Reserve (Dippenaar-Schoeman et al. 2011); Amanzi Private Game Reserve (Haddad & Butler 2018); Erfenis Dam Nature Reserve (Haddad et al. 2015); Ndumo Game Reserve (Haddad et al. 2006); Blouberg Nature Reserve (Foord et al. 2019) etc.

TAXONOMIC NOTES: Known from both sexes.

Hypsosinga lithyphantoides female and male Photo P. Webb

Hypsosinga lithyphantoides female Photo P. Webb

Hypsosinga lithyphantoides female and male ASD

Hypsosinga pygmaea (Sundevall, 1831)

COMMON NAME: Spotted False Pajama Spider

CONSERVATION STATUS: LC

NATIONAL RATIONALE: A species described by Sundevall (1831) as *Theridion pygmaeum*. It is widespread and known from Africa, North America, Europe and Asia. It has recently been identified in South Africa, where it known from four provinces (EOO=65 500 km²; AOO=24 km²; 47-1471 m a.s.l.). Due to wide global range it is listed as Least Concern.

LIFE STYLE: *Hypsosinga* make a complete orb-web probably sometimes with a retreat. Sampled mainly by sweep-netting grasses and herbs in from the Grassland and Savanna biomes (Foord et al. 2011; Haddad et al. 2013).

GLOBAL DISTRIBUTION: North America, Europe, Turkey, Israel, Caucasus, Russia to Central Asia, China, Korea, Japan and South Africa .

DISTRIBUTION IN SOUTH AFRICA: **Mpumalanga:** Loskop Dam Nature Reserve (-25.46, 29.23); Nelspruit (-25.47, 30.96). **Gauteng :** Irene (-25.87, 28.22); Ezemvelo Nature Reserve (-25.80, 28.77); Roodeplaatdam Nature Reserve (-25.64, 28.36). **KwaZulu-Natal:** Ndumo Game Reserve (-26.87, 32.24).

CONSERVATION MEASURES: Protected in the following reserves: Loskop Dam Nature Reserve; Ezemvelo Nature Reserve; Roodeplaatdam Nature Reserve; Ndumo Game Reserve; Blouberg Nature Reserve. No conservation actions are recommended.

TAXONOMIC NOTES: Known from both sexes.

Hypsosinga pygmaea female Photo Ernst Klimsa

Hypsosinga pygmaea female from Kloof Photo Peter Webb

Hypsosinga pygmaea female Tswaing Crater Nature Reserve Photo P. Webb

After Levy (1984)

Epigyne Photo ASD

UNDETERMINED SPECIES

Hypsosinga spp.

From Irene Veldt Photo P. Webb

From Delmas Photo P. Webb

From Wakefield Photo P. Webb

From Irene Veldt Photo P. Webb

From Irene Veldt Photo P. Webb

From Ezemvelo NR Photo P. Webb

From Alverstone Photo P. Webb

From Lephahlale (male) Photo P. Webb

From Lephahlale (female) Photo P.

GENUS *IDEOCAIRA* Simon, 1903

Ideocaira is endemic to South African and was described by Simon(1903). It is known from two species (World Spider Catalog 2020).

COMMON NAMES: Triangle Orb-Web Spiders

TYPE SPECIES: *Ideocaira transversa* Simon, 1903

MORPHOLOGY: TL female and male 8-10 mm. The genus is recognised by the triangular shape of the abdomen. When resting the legs are pulled close to the body. Their colour varies from yellow orange to brown. Carapace pear-shaped; eye area narrowed, more so in males; median eyes grouped together with posterior median eyes larger than anterior median eyes; lateral eyes are positioned more to the back and close together; fovea longitudinal. Abdomen triangular and anteriorly truncated. Legs: front legs are strong with strong setae on the tibiae (Dippenaar-Schoeman 2014; Smith 2005).

LIFE STYLE: They make orb-webs at night but little more is known about their behaviour. Specimens were sampled with sweep nets during the day.

TAXONOMY: Not revised.

Ideocaira sp. female from Kloof Photo Peter Webb

Ideocaira transversa Simon, 1903

COMMON NAME: Triangle Orb-Web Spider

CONSERVATION STATUS: LC

NATIONAL RATIONALE: A South African endemic described by Simon(1903) with the type locality only given as Natal. The species is recorded from four provinces including eight protected areas (EOO=553 077 km²; AOO=48 km²; 16-1732 m a.s.l.). Due to its wide geographical range, the species is therefore listed as Least Concern.

LIFE STYLE: An orb-web spider recorded from the Fynbos, Savanna and Thicket biomes.

GLOBAL DISTRIBUTION: South Africa

DISTRIBUTION IN SOUTH AFRICA: **Eastern Cape:** Jeffrey's Bay (-34.06, 24.91); Mkambathi Nature Reserve (-31.27, 30.02); Port Alfred (-33.58, 26.89); Tsitsikamma National Park (Storms River Mouth) (-33.98, 23.83); Thyspunt, 12 km WNW, Cape St Francis (-34.2056, 24.7083); Addo Elephant National Park (-33.32, 25.72). **KwaZulu-Natal:** Phinda Game Reserve (-27.72, 32.38); Kamborg Nature Reserve(-29.39, 29.67); Ndumo Game Reserve (-26.87, 32.24); Tembe Elephant Park (-27.0337, 32.4245); uMkhuze Game Reserve (-27.6217, 32.2454). **Limpopo:** Polokwane Nature Reserve (-23.9, 29.47); Lekgalameetse Nature Reserve, Farm Malta (-24.17, 30.25). **Western Cape:** De Hoop Nature Reserve (-34.45, 20.44).

CONSERVATION MEASURES: Protected in the following reserves: Addo Elephant National Park (Dippenaar-Schoeman et al. 2020); Ndumo Game Reserve; Phinda Game Reserve; Tembe Elephant Park; uMkhuze Game Reserve; Lekgalameetse Nature Reserve; Polokwane Nature Reserve; De Hoop Nature Reserve, Koppie Alleen. No conservation actions are recommended.

TAXONOMIC NOTES: Known only from the female with no illustrations.

FURTHER READING: Dippenaar-Schoeman et al. (2010); Dippenaar-Schoeman (2014); Simon (1903).

Ideocaira transversa undescribed male from Kloof Photo Peter Webb

Ideocaira transversa female from Kloof Photo Peter Webb

Ideocaira triquetra Simon, 1903

COMMON NAME: Yellow Triangle Orb-Web Spider

CONSERVATION STATUS: LC

NATIONAL RATIONALE: An Eastern Cape endemic described by Simon (1903) from Port Elizabeth. The species has been recorded from several localities throughout the province (EOO=64 670 km²; AOO= 48 km²; 1-1 364 m a.s.l.). Due to its wide geographical range, the species is listed as Least Concern.

LIFE STYLE: An orb-web spider recorded from the Fynbos, Savanna and Thicket Biome.

GLOBAL DISTRIBUTION: South Africa.

DISTRIBUTION IN SOUTH AFRICA: Eastern Cape: Mzimhlava River Mouth (-31.37, 29.58); Port Elizabeth (-33.95, 25.61); Addo Elephant National Park (-33.32, 25.72); Cape St Francis. -34.2056, 24.7083); Hogsback (-32.59, 26.92); Jeffreys Bay (-34.04, 24.94); Kei River Mouth (-32.68, 28.37); Keurkloof, farm Ferndale Baviaanskloof (-33.68, 24.83); Mkhambathi Nature Reserve (-31.32, 29.97); Port Alfred (-33.58, 26.89); Prentjiesberg (-31.18, 28.28); Storms River Mouth (-33.98, 23.83).

CONSERVATION MEASURES: No conservation actions are recommended.

TAXONOMIC NOTES: Known from both sexes.

Ideocaira triquetra female eye pattern
ASD

Ideocaira triquetra female dorsal and ventral
View from Jeffreysbay Photo Linda Wiese

After Smith (2005)

UNDETERMINED SPECIES

Ideocaira spp.

Ideocaira sp. female from Kloof Photo Peter Webb

Ideocaira sp. female from Wakefield Photo Peter Webb

Ideocaira sp. male from Hluhluwe NR
Photo Ernst Klimsa

Ideocaira sp. ? Photo Norman Larsen

GENUS *ISOXYA* Simon, 1885

Isoxya is an Afrotropical genus described by Simon (1885) and it is represented by 16 species of which six species are recorded from South Africa (World Spider Catalog 2020). The genus was removed from the synonymy of *Gasteracantha* Sundevall, 1833 by Benoit (1962).

COMMON NAMES: Isoxya Box Kite Spiders

TYPE SPECIES: *Isoxya cicatricosa* (C. L. Koch, 1844)

MORPHOLOGY: These spiders have a carapace that is usually as wide as it is long. Their abdomen is brightly decorated with yellow, red or black and white patterns. The dorsal part is hardened to form a rigid scutum bearing large spots and depressions, often prolonged laterally and posteriorly in spine like extensions. The spinnerets are surrounded by a sclerotised ring. Legs are relatively short. The eight eyes are in two rows (4:4). Males are much smaller than females and differ in colour and shape (Benoit & Emerit 1975; Emerit 1973).

LIFE STYLE: During the day they can be found in large orb-webs usually made high between trees. The web is usually decorated with small silk tufts. The egg sacs are covered with silk and they attached it to vegetation (Dippenaar-Schoeman 2014).

TAXONOMY: No recent revision of African species.

Isoxya cicatricosa female from Alverstone
Photo Peter Webb

Isoxya mossamedensis female from Irene
Photo Peter Webb

Isoxya mucronata female Photo Peter Webb

Isoxya sp. female Photo Peter Webb

Female with egg sac Photo Les Oates

Isoxya sp. female in web Photo Peter Webb

Isoxya cicatricosa (C. L. Koch, 1844)

COMMON NAME: Black and White Box Kite Spider

CONSERVATION STATUS: LC

NATIONAL RATIONALE: An African endemic described by C.L.Koch (1844) as *Gasteracantha cicatricosa* from Ethiopia. Recorded from several countries throughout Africa. In South Africa the species is known from six provinces (EOO=780 233 km²; AOO=160 km²; 5-2799 m a.s.l.). Due to its wide geographical range, the species is listed as Least Concern.

LIFE STYLE: An orb-web spider. During the day the species can be found in large orb-webs typically made high up between trees. The web is usually decorated with silk tufts. Sampled from the Forest, Fynbos, Grassland, Indian Ocean Coastal Belt, Nama Karoo, Savanna, Succulent Karoo and Thicket biomes (Foord et al. 2011; Haddad et al. 2013).

GLOBAL DISTRIBUTION: Wide spread throughout Africa.

DISTRIBUTION IN SOUTH AFRICA: **Eastern Cape:** Alexandria (-33.65, 26.4); Alicedale (-33.31, 26.08); Bathurst (-33.5, 26.84); Baviaanskloof Nature Reserve (-33.76, 24.81); Dunbrody (-33.47, 25.55); Fort Brown Kudu Reserve (-33.13, 26.62); Grahamstown (-33.3, 26.52); Hamburg (-33.29, 27.46); Jansenville (-32.93, 24.67); Kasouga (-33.63, 26.43); Kenton-on-Sea (-33.68, 26.67); King William's Town (-32.88, 27.39); Kowie (-33.45, 26.7); Pearston (-32.59, 25.15); East London (-33.01, 27.9); Port Alfred (-33.58, 26.89); Redhouse (-33.82, 25.55). **KwaZulu-Natal:** Botha's Hill (-29.7, 30.72); Champagne Castle Hotel (-29.06, 29.41); Champagne Castle (-29.08, 29.35); Durban (-29.85, 31.01); Estcourt (-29.00, 29.87); Mariannahill (-29.86, 30.83); Pietermaritzburg (-29.60, 30.38); Ngome State Forest (-27.78, 31.45); Nkandla Forest (-28.61, 31.09); Ophathe Game Reserve (-28.52, 31.66); Pongola, (Farm Vergeval) (-27.35, 31.61); Richards Bay (-28.78, 32.1); Umgeni Valley Nature Reserve (-29.47, 30.2). **Limpopo:** Naboomspruit (-24.52, 28.7). **Mpumalanga:** Barberton (-25.79, 31.04). **Northern Cape:** Nieuwoudtville (-31.37, 19.11). **Western Cape:** Cape Town (-33.91, 18.42); De Hoop Nature Reserve (-34.45, 20.44); Hermanus (-34.4, 19.25); Karoo National Park (-32.28, 22.46); Kogelberg Biosphere Reserve Kogelberg Valley. (-34.32, 18.96); Table Mountain National Park (-33.82, 18.48); Cape Town (-33.91, 18.42)

CONSERVATION MEASURES: No conservation actions are recommended. Sampled in >15 protected areas such as: Ophathe Game Reserve (Haddad & Dippenaar-Schoeman 2015); De Hoop Nature Reserve (Haddad & Dippenaar-Schoeman 2009); Karoo National Park (Dippenaar-Schoeman et al. 1999) and Table Mountain National Park.

TAXONOMIC NOTES: Last revised by Emerit (1973). Known from both sexes.

Isoxya cicatricosa female Photo Les Oates

Isoxya cicatricosa female from Alverstone Photo Peter Webb

Isoxya cicatricosa female from Alverstone Photo Peter Webb

Male ?

Habitus after Benoit (1962)

Isoxya mossamedensis Benoit, 1962

COMMON NAME: Angola Isoxya Box Kite Spider

CONSERVATION STATUS: LC

NATIONAL RATIONALE: A Southern African endemic described by Benoit (1962) from Angola. The species is rare and has been sampled in South Africa from three provinces (EOO=98 762 km²; AOO=12 km²; 400-1692 m a.s.l.). Due to its wide geographical range, the species is listed as Least Concern.

LIFE STYLE: The species makes orb-webs between vegetation. Spiders are found in the web during the day. Sampled from the Grassland and Nama Karoo biomes.

GLOBAL DISTRIBUTION: Angola and South Africa.

DISTRIBUTION IN SOUTH AFRICA: **Mpumalanga:** Ermelo (-26.51, 29.98); **Gauteng:** Irene Veld (field opposite Gem Village) (-25.89, 28.23). **Western Cape:** Cape Aardvark Nature Reserve (-33.4941, 21.0880); Fernkloof Nature Reserve (-34.86, 19.34).

CONSERVATION MEASURES: No conservation actions are recommended. Protected in the Aardvark Nature Reserve.

TAXONOMIC NOTES: Male identification is still problematic.

Isoxya mossamedensis female from Aardvark
Photo Peter Webb

Isoxya mossamedensis female dorsal and ventral view
from Irene Photo Peter Webb

Habitus after Benoit (1962)

From Fern Kloof Photos Victor Hamilton

Isoxya mucronata Walckenaer, 1841

COMMON NAME: Mucronata Box Kite Spider

CONSERVATION STATUS: LC

NATIONAL RATIONALE: An African endemic described by Walckenaer (1841) from the Democratic Republic of the Congo. In South Africa the species is known from two provinces (EOO=8 088 km²; AOO=20 km²; 416-1507 m a.s.l.). The species may however be under collected and is suspected to occur in more countries in-between. Due to its wide geographical range, the species is listed as Least Concern.

LIFE STYLE: The species makes orb-webs between vegetation. The web is usually decorated with silk tufts. Sampled from the Forest, Grassland and Savanna biomes (Foord et al. 2011; Haddad et al. 2013).

GLOBAL DISTRIBUTION: The Democratic Republic of the Congo and South Africa

DISTRIBUTION IN SOUTH AFRICA: *KwaZulu-Natal:* Howick (-29.47, 30.2); Oribi Gorge Nature Reserve (-30.71, 30.26); Pietermaritzburg (-29.6, 30.38); Umgeni River (-29.26, 30.32); St. Lucia (-27.58, 32.67). *Limpopo:* Kruger National Park (Letaba) (-22.93, 31.02).

CONSERVATION MEASURES: No conservation actions are recommended. Sampled from the following protected areas: Oribi Gorge Nature Reserve and Kruger National Park.

TAXONOMIC NOTES: Last revised by Emerit (1982). Known from both sexes.

Habitus after Emerit (1982)

Fernkloof

Isoxya mucronata female from St Lucia Photo Peter Webb

Isoxya stuhlmanni Bosenberg & Lenz, 1895

COMMON NAME: Spotted Isoxya Box Kite Spider

CONSERVATION STATUS: LC

NATIONAL RATIONALE: An African endemic described by Bösenberg and Lenz (1895) from the Democratic Republic of the Congo. The species is known from several African countries. In South Africa, the species is recorded from five provinces (EOO=377 941 km²; AOO=88 km²; 13-1902 m a.s.l.). Due to its wide geographical range, the species is listed as being of Least Concern.

LIFE STYLE: An orb-web spider. During the day, the species can be found in large orb-webs typically made high between trees. They were sampled in high numbers in coastal forests at Richard's Bay. The webs were constructed 1-2 m above-ground between plants, with individual webs often abutting (Dippenaar-Schoeman & Wassenaar 2006). Sampled from the Forest, Grassland, Indian Ocean Coastal Belt, Savanna and Thicket biomes (Foord et al. 2011; Haddad et al. 2013).

GLOBAL DISTRIBUTION: Rwanda, Tanzania, Democratic Republic of the Congo, Mozambique, Swaziland and South Africa.

DISTRIBUTION IN SOUTH AFRICA: **Eastern Cape:** East London (-33.01, 27.9); Grahamstown (-33.3, 26.52); Mazeppa Bay (-32.47, 28.64); Qachas Nek (-30.12, 28.68); Port St. Johns, Nxo forest (-31.63, 29.53); King William's Town (-32.88, 27.39); Pirie Forest (-32.72, 27.24); Port Alfred (-33.58, 26.89); Prentjiesberg (-31.18, 28.28). **Free State:** Bloemfontein (-29.11, 26.22). **KwaZulu-Natal:** Eshowe (-28.89, 31.47); Dlinza Forest near Eshowe (-28.89, 31.45); Oribi Gorge Nature Reserve (-30.71, 30.26); Ndumo Game Reserve (-26.87, 32.24); Ophathe Game Reserve (-28.52, 31.66); Richards Bay (15 km N) (-28.78, 32.1); Tembe Elephant Park (-26.94, 32.47); Umfolozi Nature Reserve (-28.3, 31.76); iSimangaliso Wetland Park, Cape Vidal. (-28.22, 32.5); Richards Bay (-28.78, 32.1). **Limpopo:** Kruger National Park, Seekoeigat (-22.93, 31.02). **Mpumalanga:** Lydenburg (-25.09, 30.46); Nelspruit (-25.47, 30.96).

CONSERVATION MEASURES: Protected in eight protected areas. No conservation actions are recommended.

TAXONOMIC NOTES: Last revised by Emerit (1973). Known only from the female but identification of male is still problematic.

Isoxya stuhlmanni female Photo Peter Webb

Isoxya stuhlmanni female from Kloof Photo P. Webb

Isoxya stuhlmanni female from Kloof Photo P. Webb

Habitus after Lessert

Isoxya tabulata (Thorell, 1859)

COMMON NAME: Yellow Isoxya Box Kite Spider

CONSERVATION STATUS: LC

NATIONAL RATIONALE: An African endemic described by Thorell (1859) from the Democratic Republic of the Congo (DRC), and known from nine African countries. In South Africa, the species is recorded from six provinces including 13 protected areas (EOO=681 893km²; AOO=268km²; 1-1399m a.s.l.). Due to its wide geographical range, the species is listed as being of Least Concern.

LIFE STYLE: An orb-web spider. During the day, the species can be found in large orb-webs usually made high between trees. The web is usually decorated with silk tufts. Sampled from the Forest, Grassland, Indian Ocean Coastal Belt, Savanna and Thicket biomes (Foord et al. 2011; Haddad et al. 2013). The species was also sampled from citrus orchards and tomato fields (Dippenaar-Schoeman et al. 2013).

GLOBAL DISTRIBUTION: Angola, the Democratic Republic of the Congo, Malawi, Swaziland, Tanzania, Zimbabwe, Mozambique and South Africa.

DISTRIBUTION IN SOUTH AFRICA: **Eastern Cape:** Addo Elephant National Park Woody Cape. (-33.32, 25.72); East London (-33.01, 27.9); King William's Town (-32.88, 27.39); Port Elizabeth (-33.95, 25.61); Groendal (-33.7094, 25.3508); Mkhambathi Nature Reserve (-31.32, 29.97). **KwaZulu-Natal:** Bluff (-29.88, 31.02); Dukuduku Forest Station (-28.37, 32.23); Durban (-29.85, 31.01); Empangeni (-28.72, 31.88); Eshowe (-28.89, 31.47); Glenmore (-31, 30.25); Hluhluwe (-28.02, 32.28); Hluhluwe Nature Reserve (-28.09, 32.1); Ifafa Beach (-30.45, 30.64); iSimangaliso Wetland Park: Cape Vidal (-28.16, 32.56), Kosi Bay Nature Reserve (-26.93, 32.87), Lake Sibaya (-27.35, 32.7), Lake St. Lucia (-28, 32.48), Mkuzi Game Reserve (-27.63, 32.25), Sodwana Bay National Park (-27.4, 32.76); Jozini (-27.42, 32.07); Lewombo Mission Station (-28, 32); Makowe (-27.96, 32.11); Margate (-30.85, 30.36); Ndumo Game Reserve (-26.87, 32.24); Ngoje Forest (-28.88, 31.38); Ngome State Forest (-27.78, 31.45); Nongoma (-27.93, 31.65); Oribi Gorge Nature Reserve (-30.71, 30.26); Pietermaritzburg (-29.6, 30.38); Pongola (Farm Vergeval) (-27.35, 31.61); Port Edward (-31.04, 30.21); Port Shepstone (-30.74, 30.44); Richards Bay (-28.78, 32.1); Scottburgh (-30.28, 30.75); Tembe Elephant Park (-26.94, 32.47); Umbonambi (-28.72, 30.02); Ubombo (-27.56, 32.08); Umfolozi Nature Reserve (-28.3, 31.76); Umkomaas (-30.2, 30.8); Uvongo (-30.82, 30.39); Valley Bush (-28, 32); Vernon Crookes Nature Reserve (-30.27, 30.57); Winkelspruit (-30.08, 30.83). **Limpopo:** Dendron (Farm Amsterdam) (-23.37, 29.32); Ellisras/ Lephale (-23.67, 27.71); Hae-

Isoxya tabulata female Photo I. Riddell

Isoxya tabulate female Photo Peter Webb

Isoxya tabulate female Photo K. Braun

After Lawrence 1937

Isoxya tabulata (continued)

Mpumalanga: Hectorspruit (-25.43, 31.68); Komatipoort (-25.43, 31.94); Komatipoort (Farm Sommerreg, 17 km SE) (-25.53, 31.82); Kruger National Park (Skukuza) (-25, 31.97); Loskop Research Station (-25.17, 29.4); Marble Hall (-24.96, 29.29); Marloth Nature Reserve (-25.35, 31.78). **North-West:** Buffelspoort Research Station (-25.62, 27.77). **Western Cape:** Saasveld Forest Station (-33.95, 22.53).

CONSERVATION MEASURES: Protected in > 20 protected areas such as Ndumo Game Reserve (Haddad et al. 2006); Tembe Elephant Park (Haddad et al. 2009); Kruger National Park (Dippenaar-Schoeman & Leroy 2003) and Addo Elephant National Park (Dippenaar-Schoeman et al. 2020). No conservation actions are recommended.

TAXONOMIC NOTES: Last revised by Emerit (1973). Known from both sexes. This species resemble *Isoxya stuhlmanni* closely.

Isoxya tabulata female from Kloof Photo P. Webb

Isoxya tabulate female Photo Hannes Mitchell

Isoxya yatesi Emerit, 1973

COMMON NAME: Yates' Box Kite Spider

CONSERVATION STATUS: DDT

NATIONAL RATIONALE: A South African endemic described by Emerit (1973) from Pinetown. The species is known from two provinces (EEO=107 238 km²; AOO=16 km²; 353-1407 m a.s.l.). The species is rare and undercollected. Some more sampling is needed to collect the male and to determine the species' range. Therefore, listed as Data Deficient for Taxonomic reasons.

LIFE STYLE: An orb-web spider. During the day the species can be found in large orb-webs usually made high between trees. The species is known from the Savanna, Grassland and Bushveld biomes (Foord et al 2011; Haddad et al. 2013).

GLOBAL DISTRIBUTION: South Africa.

DISTRIBUTION IN SOUTH AFRICA: *KwaZulu-Natal*: Umbonambi (-28.73, 30.02); Pinetown (-29.81, 30.85). *Limpopo*: Haenertsburg Wolkberg Nature Reserve (-23.94, 29.95); Atherstone Nature Reserve (-24.416, 26.750).

CONSERVATION MEASURES: Some more sampling is needed to collect the male and to determine the species' range. Protected in the following reserves: Atherstone Nature Reserve and Wolkberg Nature Reserve. .

TAXONOMIC NOTES: Known only from the female. Not revised.

Isoxya yatesi female dorsal view ASD

Isoxya yatesi after Emerit (1973)

Isoxya yatesi female ventral view ASD

Isoxya yatesi female lateral view ASD

NEW OR ONLY VARIATIONS??

Isoxya spp.

undetermined

Female from Swaziland Photo P. Webb

Female from St Lucia Photo P. Webb

Female from Eastern Cape Photo Linda Wiese

Westville Durban

GENUS *KILIMA* Grasshoff, 1970

Kilima is endemic to African and was described by Grasshoff (1970). It is represented by three species of which one is known from South Africa (World Spider Catalog 2020).

COMMON NAMES: Kilima Grass Orb-Web Spiders

TYPE SPECIES: *Kilima decens* (Blackwall, 1866)

MORPHOLOGY: Size: TL female and male 7-9 mm. Carapace is elongate with dark median longitudinal band. Abdomen with a narrow orange band bordered by a thin band that varies from white to brown followed by a broader dark brown band with scalloped edge. Legs are similar to carapace in colour. The genus resembles the grassland species *Nesoscona moreli* but in this genus the abdominal longitudinal bands are in almost a straight line.

LIFE STYLE: *Kilima decens* is commonly found on grasses, where they blend in with their elongated, straw-coloured bodies. Their webs are made during the night and removed early in the morning. They rest during the day on nearby vegetation, usually grass. They prey on a wide variety of flying and jumping insects (Dippenaar-Schoeman 2014).

TAXONOMY: Genus not yet revised.

FURTHER READING: Grasshoff (1970).

Kilima decens female Photo Peter Webb

Kilima decens female from Mpetsane
Photo Allen Jones

Kilima decens female from Bloemfontein
Photo Johan van Zyl

Kilima decens (Blackwall, 1866)

COMMON NAME: Kilima Grass Orb-Web Spider

CONSERVATION STATUS: LC

NATIONAL RATIONALE: An African endemic described by Blackwall (1866) as *Epeira decens* from Tanzania. The species is widespread throughout Africa. It was sampled from Lesotho and South Africa and is known from all the provinces (EOO=779 604 km²; AOO=188 km²; 1-1986 m a.s.l.). Due to its wide geographical range, the species is listed as Least Concern.

LIFE STYLE: The species usually makes large orb-webs in grass at night. Sampled from the Fynbos, Indian Ocean Coastal Belt, Grassland and Savanna biomes (Foord et al. 2011; Haddad et al. 2013). It was also sampled from potato and pumpkin fields (Dippenaar-Schoeman et al. 2013).

GLOBAL DISTRIBUTION: Widespread throughout Africa.

DISTRIBUTION IN SOUTH AFRICA: **Eastern Cape:** Grahamstown (-33.3, 26.52); Jeffrey's Bay (-34.06, 24.91); Mkambathi Nature Reserve (-31.02, 30.23). **Free State:** Bloemfontein (-29.11, 26.22); Mpetsane Conservation Estate (-28.92, 27.58); Fouriesburg (-28.61, 28.23); Oranjeville (-26.99, 28.2); Vredefort (-27, 27.37). **Gauteng:** Ezemvelo Nature Reserve (-25.8, 28.77); Johannesburg (-26.2, 28.04); Norscott Nature Reserve (-26.2, 28.04); Pretoria/Tshwane (-25.74, 28.19); Pretoria/Tshwane (Irene, Smuts House) (-25.89, 28.23); Rietveldam Nature Reserve (-25.85, 28.16); Roodeplaat Research Station (-25.66, 28.35). **KwaZulu-Natal:** Kamberg Nature Reserve (-29.39, 29.67); iSimangaliso Wetland Park (Kosi Bay Nature Reserve) (-26.93, 32.87); Margate (-30.85, 30.36). **Limpopo:** Mosdene Nature Reserve (-24.52, 28.7); Vaalwater (-24.29, 28.11); Warmbaths/Bela-Bela (-24.88, 28.29); Kruger National Park (-22.93, 31.02). **Mpumalanga:** Belfast (-25.69, 30.04); Blyde River Canyon Nature Reserve (-24.58, 30.82); Delmas (-26.14, 28.68); Loskop Dam Nature Reserve (-25.46, 29.23); Sabie (-25.1, 30.78); Standerton (-26.94, 29.23). **North-West:** Barberspan (-26.62, 25.58); Borakalalo Game Reserve (-25.14, 27.82); Hartbeespoortdam (-25.73, 27.85). **Northern Cape:** Suffolk farm nr Hopetown (-29.58, 24.24). **Western Cape:** Stellenbosch (-33.93, 18.85).

CONSERVATION MEASURES: Protected in >15 reserves such as Mkambathi Nature Reserve (Dippenaar-Schoeman et al. 2011; Kruger national park (Dippenaar-Schoeman & Leroy 2003. No conservation actions are recommended.

TAXONOMIC NOTES: Revised by Grasshoff (1970). Known from both sexes.

Kilima decens female Photo Koos Geldenhuys

Kilima decens female
Photo Peter Webb

Kilima decens female from
Mpetsane Photo Allen Jones

Kilima decens female Photo Johan van Zyl

Epigyne after Grasshoff (1970)

Epigyne Photo ASD

GENUS *LARINIA* Simon, 1874

Larinia is a genus described by Simon (1874) and it is represented by 58 species that have a worldwide distribution. Eleven species are known from Africa and three are so far recorded from South Africa (World Spider Catalog 2020).

COMMON NAMES: Grass Orb-Web Spiders

TYPE SPECIES: *Larinia lineata* (Lucas, 1846)

MORPHOLOGY: Medium-sized araneids with a narrow, elongated body. Carapace longer than it is wide; with a short, grooved longitudinal fovea; anterior median eyes largest; median ocular quadrangle appreciably wider in front than behind; chelicerae with 3-4 promarginal and retromarginal teeth. Abdomen distinctly longer than wide. Epigynum of female bears a slender scape with rigid attachment at base; scape frequently breaks off. Legs I longest, legs III shortest; They can be confused with *Kilima decens* but here the median lines with slight curves (Dippenaar-Schoeman 2014; Dippenaar-Schoeman & Haddad 2014).

LIFE STYLE: This is a typical grassland species, resembling grass in shape and colour. They construct loosely woven webs in grass. They are not easily seen and usually sampled with a sweep net. When at rest they stretch their body and legs along a blade of grass.

TAXONOMY: Last report on African *Larinia* by Grasshoff (1970, 1971).

Larinia sp. female in web Photo Allen Jones

Larinia sp. female in web Photo Allen Jones

Larinia sp. female Photo Allen Jones

Larinia sp. male in web Photo Allen Jones

Larinia bifida Tullgren, 1910

COMMON NAME: Larinia Grass Orb-Web Spider

CONSERVATION STATUS: LC

NATIONAL RATIONALE: An African endemic described by Tullgren (1910) from Tanzania. The species has been recorded from seven African countries. In South Africa, it is known from five provinces (EOO=361 049 km²; AOO=36 km²; 3-1730 m a.s.l.). Due to its wide geographical range, the species is listed Least Concern.

LIFE STYLE: An orb-web spider, which constructs orb-webs in grass at night. This is a typical grassland species, resembling grass in shape and colour. They are not easily seen and are usually sampled with a sweep net. When at rest they stretch their body and legs along a blade of grass. Sampled from the Grassland and Fynbos biomes.

GLOBAL DISTRIBUTION: Botswana, Central African Republic, Democratic Republic of the Congo, Malawi, Tanzania, Seychelles and South Africa.

DISTRIBUTION IN SOUTH AFRICA: **Eastern Cape:** Mountain Zebra National Park (-32.24, 25.43). **Free State :** Kalkfontein Dam Nature Reserve (-29.51, 25.25); Sterkfontein Dam Nature Reserve (-28.48,29.01); Mpetsane Conservation Estate (-28.92, 27.58). **Gauteng:** Kliprivierberg Nature Reserve (-26.27,28.08); Tswaing Crater Nature Reserve (-25.42, 28.08). **North West :** Ventersdorp.-26.32 26.82). **Western Cape:** Jacobsbaai, Saldanha Bay (-33.15, 18.03); Cape Town (-33.91, 18.42); Table Mountain National Park (-33.82, 18.48).

CONSERVATION MEASURES: No conservation actions are recommended. Sampled from six protected areas such as Mountain Zebra National Park (Dippenaar- Schoeman 2006) and Table Mountain National Park.

TAXONOMIC NOTES: Revised by Grasshoff (1970). Known only from the female.

Larinia bifida females in web from Mpetsane Photo Allen Jones

After Grasshoff (1970)

Larinia bifida males in web from Mpetsane Photo Allen Jones

After Grasshoff (1970)

Larinia chloris (Audouin, 1826)

COMMON NAME: Larinia Grass Orb-Web Spider

CONSERVATION STATUS: LC

NATIONAL RATIONALE: A species described by Audouin (1826) as *Epeira chloris* with a wide distribution in Africa and western Asia. In South Africa, the species is known from five provinces (EOO=559 467 km²; AOO=32 km²; 4-1909 m a.s.l.). Due to its wide geographical range, the species is listed as Least Concern.

GLOBAL DISTRIBUTION: North and East Africa, Turkey, Mozambique, India, Bangladesh and South Africa.

DISTRIBUTION IN SOUTH AFRICA: **Eastern Cape:** Thyspunt (-34.192, 24.712); Addo Elephant National Park (-33.32, 25.72). **Limpopo:** Potgietersrus/Mokopane (-24.17, 29.00). **Mpumalanga:** Verloren Vallei Nature Reserve (-25.53, 30.13). **Western Cape:** Borrelfontein, 8 km W of Gouritz Mouth (-34.33, 21.85); De Hoop Nature Reserve (-34.45, 20.44); Swartberg Nature Reserve (Gamkaskloof) (-33.36, 21.69). **Northern Cape:** Tswalu Kalahari Reserve (-27.3, 22.44).

LIFE STYLE: An orb-web spider that constructs their webs in the grass. Known from the Thicket, Fynbos, Savanna and Grassland biomes (Foord et al. 2011).

CONSERVATION MEASURES: No conservation actions are recommended. There are no known threats to the species. Protected in five reserves such as Swartberg Nature Reserve (Gamkaskloof) (Dippenaar-Schoeman et al. 2005) and Tswalu Kalahari Reserve (Dippenaar-Schoeman et al. 2018).

TAXONOMIC NOTES: Revised by Grasshoff (1970). Known from both sexes.

After Grasshoff (1970).

Larinia bifida after ASD

Larinia bifida female Photo Peter Webb

Larinia bifida female Photo Martie Rheeder

Larinia bifida female Photo Ernst Klimsa

Larinia natalensis (Grasshoff, 1971)

COMMON NAME: Natal Larinia Grass Orb-Web Spider

CONSERVATION STATUS: LC

NATIONAL RATIONALE: A South African endemic described by Grasshoff (1971) as *Drexelia natalensis*, with type locality only given as Natal. This species is known from six provinces (EOO=448 867 km²; AOO=48 km²; 55-1842 m a.s.l.). Due to its geographical range, the species is listed as Least Concern.

GLOBAL DISTRIBUTION: South Africa.

DISTRIBUTION IN SOUTH AFRICA: **Gauteng:** Klipriviersberg Nature Reserve (-26.27, 28.08). **KwaZulu-Natal:** Empangeni (-28.72, 31.88); Enseleni Nature Reserve (-28.68, 32.05); Giant's Castle Nature Reserve (-29.23, 29.48); Isandlwane Nature Reserve (-28.338, 30.667); Dukuduku Forest Station (-28.37, 32.23). **Limpopo:** Legalameetse Nature Reserve (-23.82, 30.16); Polokwane Nature Reserve (-23.537, 29.7145). **North West:** Ventersdorp (-26.32, 26.82). **Northern Cape:** Benfontein Game Reserve (-28.82, 24.82). **Western Cape:** Swartberg Nature Reserve (Gamkaskloof) (-33.36, 21.69); De Hoop Nature Reserve (-34.45, 20.44).

LIFE STYLE: An orb-web spider that constructs their webs in grass. Known from the Fynbos, Indian Ocean Coastal Belt, Grassland and Savanna biomes (Foord et al. 2011). The species was also sampled from cotton fields (Dippenaar-Schoeman et al. 2013).

CONSERVATION MEASURES: There are no known threats to the species. Protected in ten reserves such as De Hoop Nature Reserve (Haddad & Dippenaar-Schoeman 2009); Polokwane Nature Reserve (Dippenaar et al. 2008); Swartberg Nature Reserve (Dippenaar-Schoeman et al. 2005) and Legalameetse Nature Reserve (Foord et al. 2016).

TAXONOMIC NOTES: Known only from female.

Epigynum after Grasshoff (1970)

Larinia natalensis female Photo ASD

UNDETERMINED SPECIES

GENUS *LARINIOIDES* Caporiacco, 1934

Genus described by Caporiacco (1934) represented by seven species. Most of species with very wide distribution throughout Europe, North Africa to Central Asia, Russia and introduced in North America (World Spider Catalog 2020).

COMMON NAMES: Larinioides Orb-web Spiders

TYPE SPECIES: *Larinioides suspicax* (O. Pickard-Cambridge, 1876)

MORPHOLOGY: These orb-weaving spiders have large, bulbous, oval-shaped abdomens, which are dorsoventrally flattened. The abdomen ranges in color including black, grey, red and olive, and the carapace features a lighter colored, arrow-shaped pattern that points towards the cephalothorax. Their legs have a striped pattern matching the carapace with strong setae. The two pairs of forward legs are very long (typically equal to the entire body length) while their rear legs are shorter. Males tend to be smaller and paler in color than females.

LIFE STYLE: Orb-web vertical in grass vegetation and less than 1 m above ground. Retreat always present.

TAXONOMY: Several species have been sampled that are still unnamed. More material, especially of males, is needed for identification purposes and to describe if it is a new species.

Mpetsane Photo A. Jones

Umhlanga Photo P. Webb

Jeffreysbay Photo L. Wiese

Legalameetse NR Photo P. Webb

Sabie Photo P. Webb

Irene Photo P. Webb

GENUS *LIPOCREA* Thorell, 1878

Lipocrea is a genus described by Thorell (1878) and it is represented by four species with only one species recorded from Africa (World Spider Catalog 2020).

COMMON NAMES: Long Tailed Grass Orb-Web Spiders

TYPE SPECIES: *Lipocrea fusiformis* (Thorell, 1877)

MORPHOLOGY: Size: TL female and male 7-8 mm. These spiders have straw-coloured bodies and legs. Carapace is elongate pear-shaped but narrower in the eye region; fovea elongate, with a narrow longitudinal band dorsally. Abdomen straw-coloured frequently with paired black spots; oval, elongate with a narrow tip anteriorly and a slight hump above the spinnerets. Their legs are very long and decorated with spots and setae; same colour as body; bear setae with dark spots at their bases (Grasshoff 1970).

LIFE STYLE: They make orb-webs in grass at night and remove them early in the morning.

TAXONOMY: Only one species from Africa described by Grasshoff (1970).

Lipocrea longissimima female from Irene Photo Peter Webb

Lipocrea longissima (Simon, 1881)

COMMON NAME: Lipocrea Grass Orb-Web Spider

CONSERVATION STATUS: LC

NATIONAL RATIONALE: An African endemic described by Simon (1881) as *Larinia longissima*. The species is widely distributed throughout Africa. In South Africa it is known from seven provinces (EOO=550 584 km²; AOO=84 km²; 3-1706 m a.s.l.). There are no significant threat to the species and due to its wide geographical range, the species is listed as Least Concern.

GLOBAL DISTRIBUTION: Lesotho, Botswana and South Africa.

DISTRIBUTION IN SOUTH AFRICA: **Free State:** Bloemfontein (-29.11, 26.22); Erfenis Dam Nature Reserve (-28.5, 26.8). **Eastern Cape:** Mkambathi Nature Reserve (-31.02, 30.23). **Gauteng:** Ezemvelo Nature Reserve (-25.8, 28.77); Faerie Glenn Nature Reserve (-25.7, 28.19). **KwaZulu-Natal:** Empangeni (-28.72, 31.88); Hluhluwe Game Reserve (-28.02, 32.28); iSimangaliso Wetland Park (Mkuzi Game Reserve) (-27.63, 32.25); iSimangaliso Wetland Park, Hells Gate (-28.011, 32.443); Ndumo Game Reserve (-26.87, 32.24); Ngoje Forest (-28.88, 31.38); Nkandla Forest (-28.61, 31.09); Richards Bay (-28.78, 32.1); Tembe Elephant Park (-26.94, 32.47); Charters Creek Champ (-28.199, 32.414). **Limpopo:** Makalali Nature Reserve (-24.34, 30.93); Lekgalameetse Nature Reserve (-23.82, 30.84). **Mpumalanga:** Brondal (-25.35, 30.84); Graskop (-24.93, 30.84). **Western Cape:** Worcester (-33.64, 19.47); Bontebok National Park (-34.07, 20.45).

LIFE STYLE: The species makes orb-webs in grass and is known from Fynbos, Forest, Indian Ocean Coastal Belt, Grassland and Savanna biomes (Foord et al. 2011; Haddad et al. 2013). The species has also been sampled from avocado (Dippenaar-Schoeman et al. 2005) and pecan orchards, as well as tomato fields (Dippenaar-Schoeman et al. 2013).

CONSERVATION MEASURES: There are no known threats to the species. Sampled from >10 protected areas such as Mkambathi Nature Reserve (Dippenaar-Schoeman et al 2011); Erfenis Dam Nature Reserve (Fourie et al. 2013) and Ndumo Game Reserve (Haddad et al. 2006)

TAXONOMIC NOTES: Revised by Grasshoff (1970). Known from both sexes.

Lipocrea longissima female ASD

Lipocrea longissima male ASD

Lipocrea longissima female from Irene Photo Peter Webb

GENUS *MAHEMBEA* Grasshoff, 1970

Mahembea described by Grasshoff (1970) is a monotypic and endemic to Africa (World Spider Catalog 2020).

COMMON NAMES: Mahembea Grass Orb-Web Spiders

TYPE SPECIES: *Mahembea hewitti* (Lessert, 1930)

MORPHOLOGY: Size: TL female and male 7-8 mm. Carapace elongate; straw coloured to yellow orange; with a median longitudinal band. Abdomen elongate extend past spinnerets; with thin paired longitudinal bands. Legs same colour as body; bear setae with dark spots at their bases (Grasshoff 1970).

LIFE STYLE: They make orb-webs in grass at night and remove them early in the morning.

TAXONOMY: Known from both sexes.

Mahembea hewitti female Photo Peter Webb

Mahembea hewitti female in web Photo W. Schmidt

Mahemba hewitti (Lessert, 1930)

COMMON NAME: Hewitt's Grass Orb-Web Spider

CONSERVATION STATUS: LC

NATIONAL RATIONALE: An African endemic described from the Democratic Republic of the Congo by Lessert (1930), as *Larinia hewittii*. The species is under collected and is suspected to occur in more countries. In South Africa, the species is known from five provinces (EOO=183 704 km²; AOO=36 km²; 29-1556 m a.s.l.). Due to its wide geographical range, the species is listed as Least Concern.

GLOBAL DISTRIBUTION: Democratic Republic of the Congo to South Africa.

DISTRIBUTION IN SOUTH AFRICA: **Gauteng:** Roodeplaatdam Nature Reserve (-25.64, 28.36). **KwaZulu-Natal:** Mount Edgecombe (-29.68, 31.03); Ngome State Forest (-27.78, 31.45); Richards Bay (-28.78, 32.1); iSimangaliso Wetland park, Sodwana Bay National Park (-27.4, 32.76). **Limpopo:** Polokwane Nature Reserve (-23.9, 29.47); Lekgalameetse Nature Reserve (-23.82, 30.16). **Mpumalanga:** Marble Hall (-24.96, 29.29). **North West :** Kgaswane Mountain Reserve (-25.72, 27.18).

LIFE STYLE: The species makes orb-webs in grass. It is known from the Forest Indian Ocean Coastal Belt and Savanna biomes (Foord et al. 2011). The species was also sampled from sugar cane fields (Dippenaar-Schoeman et al. 2013).

CONSERVATION MEASURES: There are no known threats to the species. Protected in >6 protected areas. Polokwane Nature Reserve (Dippenaar et al. 2008); Lekgalameetse Nature Reserve (Foord et al. 2016) and Roodeplaat Dam Nature Reserve (Dippenaar-Schoeman et al. 1989).

TAXONOMIC NOTES: Revised by Grasshoff (1970). Known from both sexes.

Mahemba hewitti female from Loskopdam Photo Peter Webb

Mahemba hewitti female Photo ASD

Mahemba hewitti female Photo Ernst Klimsa

After Grasshoff (1970)

GENUS *MEGARANEUS* Lawrence, 1968

A monotypic African endemic genus described by Lawrence (1968)(World Spider Catalog 2020).

COMMON NAMES: Large Spiky Orb-Web Spider

TYPE SPECIES: *Megaraneus gabonensis* (Lucas, 1858)

MORPHOLOGY: These large araneids (30-21 mm) bear superficial resemblance to bark spiders. In the holotype the carapace is blackish brown, sometimes reddish; covered by minute round wart-like tubercles; sternum is blackish; ventral surface is covered with golden hair. The abdomen has three pairs of blunt lateral sub-angular tubercles and there are two pairs of large round sigillae and about 50 smaller pit like impressions; variable pattern of yellow markings on a black background. Legs are black with front legs banded; leg I shorter than IV. Sexual dimorphism occurs in size. Male resembles female in basic abdominal shape but is very small.

LIFE STYLE: An orb-web spider species.

TAXONOMY: Known from both sexes. This genus resembles members of the genus *Acanthepeira* Marx, 1883 that is presently only known from North and South America. Several species have been sampled that could be members of *Megaraneus* or else *Acanthepeira* which is newly recorded from Africa

Megaraneus gabonensis from Mozambique Photo Len de Beer

Photo Ernst Klimsa

Photo Len de Beer

Megaraneus gabonensis (Lucas, 1858)

COMMON NAME: Gabon Megaraneus Orb-Web Spider

CONSERVATION STATUS: LC

NATIONAL RATIONALE: An African endemic described from Gabon by Lucas (1858) as *Epeira gabonensis*. This species has been recorded from seven African countries. In South Africa, the species is known from a single province (EOO=3 933 km²; AOO=16 km²; 51-93 m a.s.l.). Due to its wide geographical range, the species is listed as Least Concern.

GLOBAL DISTRIBUTION: Angola, Cameroon, Congo Republic, Gabon, Sierra Leone, Mozambique and South Africa.

DISTRIBUTION IN SOUTH AFRICA: KwaZulu-Natal: Dukuduku Forest Station (-28.37, 32.23) Lake Sibaya (-27.35, 32.70); Tembe Elephant Park (-26.94, 32.47); iSimangaliso Wetland park, Sodwana Bay National Park (-27.4, 32.76); iSimangaliso Wetland park, Kosi Bay Nature Reserve (-26.93, 32.87).

LIFE STYLE: An orb-web spider with the web consisting of 25-30 radii with 25 viscid spirals. The free zone is narrow and the hub composed of a small rounded area (Lawrence 1968). Sampled from the Forest, Indian Coastel Belt and Savanna biomes (Foord et al. 2011).

CONSERVATION MEASURES: There are no known threats to the species. Protected in three protected areas.

TAXONOMIC NOTES: Redescribed by Lawrence (1968). Known from both sexes.

Megaraneus gabonensis from Tembe GR Photo Hennie de Klerk

Megaraneus gabonensis ventral view Photo Len de Beer

Megaraneus gabonensis Photo Len de Beer

After Lawrence (1968)

MEGARANEUS OR ACANTHEPEIRA ???

Megaraneus spp.

Lekgalameetse NR female Photo P. Webb

Male?

Thyspunt female Photo Linda Wiese

Astri Leroy

Lajuma

Maybe same as *Acanthepeira* ??

GENUS *NEMOSCOLUS* Simon, 1895

Nemoscolus is a genus described by Simon (1895) and it is known from 14 species of which 13 are known from Africa and four from South Africa (World Spider Catalog 2020).

COMMON NAME: Stone-Nest Spiders

TYPE SPECIES: *Nemoscolus laurae* (Simon, 1868)

MORPHOLOGY: Size: TL female 4-6 mm, male 3-5 mm. These small spiders have slightly elongate bodies. Carapace is pear-shaped and narrower in eye region. Abdomen is round oval; it is usually whitish with median and lateral longitudinal bands merging posteriorly. Their legs are similar in colour to the carapace and are kept tightly against the body. Males are a little smaller than females.

LIFE STYLE: Orb-web spiders that make a stone nest in the centre of the orb-web. The webs are usually made in grass. The web lacks a stabilimentum. A small conical or helicoid retreat is made of material such as soil particles, silk and vegetable matter (Lawrence, 1964). The opening of the tube is in the centre of the horizontal orb-web, and the conical tube serves as a retreat and a repository for eggs. The spider sits in the entrance of the web waiting for prey. Prey is usually jumping insects like second-instar locusts (Dippenaar-Schoeman & Haddad 2014); Dippenaar-Schoeman 2014).

TAXONOMY: African species not revised. Most of the species based on short descriptions without any drawings causing problems with placement of species.

Nemoscolus tubicola web with stone retreat
Photo Peter Webb

Nemoscolus cotti undescribed female Photo
Peter Webb

Nemoscolus sp. with stone retreat Photo P. Webb

Nemoscolus sp. Photo Peter Webb

Nemoscolus sp. with very long stone retreat
Peter Webb

Nemoscolus sp. Photo Peter Webb

Nemoscolus cotti Lessert, 1933

COMMON NAME: Cott's Stone-Nest Spider

CONSERVATION STATUS: LC

NATIONAL RATIONALE: A Southern African endemic described by Lessert (1933) from Mozambique. This species has been recorded from three countries. In South Africa, the species is known from seven provinces (EOO=427 772 km²; AOO=64 km²; 93-1838 m a.s.l.). Due to its wide geographical range, the species is listed as Least Concern.

GLOBAL DISTRIBUTION: Zimbabwe, Mozambique and South Africa.

DISTRIBUTION IN SOUTH AFRICA: **Eastern Cape:** Prentjiesberg (-31.18, 28.28). **Free State:** Erfenis Dam Nature Reserve (-28.5, 26.8); Amanzi Private Game Reserve (-28.62, 26.68). **Gauteng:** Irene Gem Village Field (-25.89, 28.23). **KwaZulu-Natal:** Garden Castle (-29.75, 29.2); Tembe Elephant Park (-26.94, 32.47). **Limpopo:** Kruger National Park, Mopani, Tsendze (-23.688, 31.518); Kruger National Park, Mopani, Dzombo (-23.452, 31.384); Blouberg Nature Reserve (-22.99, 29.04); Lephahlale (-23.4, 28.05); Marakele National Park (-24.531, 27.4977); Goro Game Ranch (-22.99, 29.43). **Mpumalanga:** Kruger National Park, Pretoriuskop, Kambeni (-25.153, 31.253); Kruger National Park, Pretoriuskop, Numbi (-25.140, 31.208); Kruger National Park, Pretoriuskop, Shabeni (-25.123, 31.237). **Northern Cape:** Hopetown (Farm Suffolk) (-29.58, 24.24).

LIFE STYLE: An orb-web spider that makes a stone nest in the centre of the orb-web usually in grass. It is known from the Savanna, Nama Karoo and Grassland biomes (Foord et al. 2011; Haddad et al. 2013).

CONSERVATION MEASURES: There are no known threats to the species. Protected in six protected areas such as Erfenis Dam Nature Reserve (Fourie et al. 2013); Kruger National Park; Blouberg Nature Reserve (Foord et al. 2019) and Marakele National Park (Dippenaar-Schoeman et al. 2020).

TAXONOMIC NOTES: Not revised. Known only from the male. Female collected but still undescribed.

Nemoscolus cotti from Irene Photo Peter Webb

Nemoscolus cotti male and female
Photo ASD

After Lessert (1933)

Nemoscolus cotti undescribed female from Irene Photo Peter Webb

Nemoscolus obscurus Simon, 1897

COMMON NAME: Stone-Nest Spider

CONSERVATION STATUS: DDT

NATIONAL RATIONALE: A South African endemic described by Simon (1897) with type locality given only as “Transvaal”. The species is known from three localities that are about 100.61 km² apart. Too little is known about the location, habitat and threats of this taxon for a full assessment to be made. More sampling is needed, to collect the male and determine the species’ range. Therefore listed as Data Deficient for Taxonomic reasons.

LIFE STYLE: An orb-web spider. The species makes a stone nest in the centre of the orb-web in grass. This species is known from the Savanna Biome (Foord et al. 2011).

GLOBAL DISTRIBUTION: South Africa.

DISTRIBUTION IN SOUTH AFRICA: type locality only as “Transvaal”*. **Gauteng:** Irene Gem Village Field (-25.89, 28.23). **North-West:** Hartebeespoort Experimental Farm (-25.60, 27.82); Pilanesberg Nature Reserve (-25.25, 27.08).

CONSERVATION MEASURES: Protected in the Pilanesberg Nature Reserve. More sampling is needed, to collect the male and determine the species’ range.

TAXONOMIC NOTES: Not revised known only from the female.

Nemoscolus obscurus female on retreat
Photo P. Webb

Nemoscolus obscurus female from Irene Photo P. Webb

Nemoscolus tubicola (Simon, 1887)

COMMON NAME: Tube Stone-Nest Spider

CONSERVATION STATUS: LC

NATIONAL RATIONALE: A southern African endemic described by Simon (1887) as *Cyclosa tubicola* from Grahamstown. The species has also been recorded from Namibia. In South Africa, it is known from seven provinces (EOO=1 049 472 km²; AOO=76 km²; 54-1513 m a.s.l.). Due to its wide geographical range, the species is listed as being of Least Concern.

GLOBAL DISTRIBUTION: Namibia, Swaziland and South Africa.

DISTRIBUTION IN SOUTH AFRICA: **Eastern Cape:** Baviaanskloof Nature Reserve (-33.76, 24.81); Grahamstown (-33.3, 26.52); Middelburg (-31.49, 24.99); Mountain Zebra National Park (-32.24, 25.43). **Gauteng:** Roodeplaatdam Nature Reserve (-25.64, 28.36). **Limpopo:** Blouberg Nature Reserve (-22.99, 29.04); Lhuvhondo Nature Reserve (-23.03, 29.45); Little Leigh (-22.95, 29.87); Springbok Flats (Tuinplaas) (-24.56, 28.46). **Northern Cape:** Richtersveld Transfrontier National Park (-28.25, 17.17); Kimberley (-28.73, 24.76); Tswalu Game Reserve (-27.3, 22.44). **North West:** Rustenburg (-25.65, 27.22). **Western Cape:** Karoo National Park (-32.28, 22.46); Prince Albert (-33.22, 22.03); Witsand Nature Reserve (-34.39, 20.85); Bontebok National Park (-34.07, 20.45); Worcester (-33.64, 19.47)

LIFE STYLE: An spider. The species makes a orb-web with a stone nest in the centre of the web in grass. Sampled from the Fynbos, Grassland, Nama Karoo, Savanna, Succulent Karoo and Thicket biomes (Foord et al. 2011; Haddad et al. 2013).

CONSERVATION MEASURES: There are no known threats to the species. Protected in 10 protected areas such as Bontebok National Park (Dippenaar-Schoeman 2020); (Mountain Zebra National Park (Dippenaar-Schoeman 2006); Roodeplaatdam Nature Reserve (Dippenaar-Schoeman et al. 1989); Blouberg Nature Reserve (Foord et al. 2019); Richtersveld Transfrontier National Park (Dippenaar-Schoeman 2020); Tswalu Kalahari Reserve (Dippenaar-Schoeman et al. 2018).

TAXONOMIC NOTES: Not revised. Known only from the female.

Nemoscolus tubicola web with stone retreat
Photo Peter Webb

Nemoscolus tubicola female Photo Les Oates

Retreat after Simon (1887)

After Dippenaar-Schoeman & Van den Berg 2010

Nemoscolus vigintipunctatus Simon, 1897

COMMON NAME: Spotted Stone-Nest Spider

CONSERVATION STATUS: LC

NATIONAL RATIONALE: A South African endemic described by Simon (1897) from the type locality only listed as “Transvaal”. It is known from eight provinces including seven protected areas (EEO=637 683 km²; AOO=52 km²; 20-1646 m a.s.l.). The species has also been recorded from Zimbabwe. Due to its wide geographical range, the species is listed as being of Least Concern.

GLOBAL DISTRIBUTION: Zimbabwe and South Africa.

DISTRIBUTION IN SOUTH AFRICA: **Eastern Cape:** Prentjiesberg (-31.18, 28.28). **Free State:** Mpetsane Conservation Estate (-28.92, 27.58). **Gauteng:** Abe Bailey Nature Reserve (-26.36, 27.4); Irene, Smuts House (-25.89, 28.23); Ezemvelo Nature Reserve -25.80, 28.77. **KwaZulu-Natal:** Cathedral Peak (-28.94, 29.19); Richards Bay (-28.78, 32.1); iSimangaliso Wetland Park (Lake Sibaya) (-27.35, 32.70). **Limpopo:** Lhuvhondo Nature Reserve (-23.03, 29.45); Makalali Nature Reserve (-24.34, 30.93); Kruger National Park (-22.93, 31.02). **North West:** Kgaswane Mountain Reserve (-25.72, 27.18). **Western Cape:** Beaufort West (Farm Katdoornkuil) (-32.42, 22.47); Dwarsrivier, Sanddrift (-32.47, 19.27)

LIFE STYLE: An orb-web spider. The species makes a stone nest in the centre of the orb-web in grass. The stone nest observed in Irene was long elongated. Sampled from the Fynbos, Forest, Indian Coastal Belt, Grassland, Savanna and Succulent Karoo biomes (Foord et al. 2011; Haddad et al. 2013).

CONSERVATION MEASURES: There are no known threats to the species. Protected in seven protected areas such as Makalali Nature Reserve (Whitmore et al. 2001); Lhuvhondo Nature Reserve (Foord et al. 2002) and Kruger National Park (Dippenaar-Schoeman & Leroy 2003).

TAXONOMIC NOTES: Not revised. Known from only the female.

Nemoscolus vigintipunctatus female from Irene Photo Peter Webb

Retreat from Irene Photo P. Webb

Nemoscolus vigintipunctatus female from Ezemvelo NR Photo Peter Webb

UNDETERMINED SPECIES

Nemoscolus spp.

Species from Irene

Species from Aardvark NR

STILL UNKNOWN NOT SEEN

GENUS *NEMOSPIZA* Simon, 1903

Monotypic genus known from one South African endemic species (World Spider Catalog 2020).

COMMON NAMES: Nemospiza Orb-Web Spiders

TYPE SPECIES: *Nemospiza conspicillata* Simon, 1903

MORPHOLOGY: Size TL female 3 mm. Carapace smooth and hairless, olive green with black reticulation. Abdomen is cylindrical, dark above. Only recorded from “Transvaal”

ABUNDANCE: Very rare

LIFE STYLE: Unknown.

TAXONOMY: Monotypic

STILL UNKNOWN

***Nemospiza conspicillata* Simon, 1903**

COMMON NAME: Nemospiza Orb-Web Spider

CONSERVATION STATUS: DDT

NATIONAL RATIONALE: A South African endemic described in 1903, from the type locality given as “Transvaal”. The species is only known from one locality, Makalali Nature Reserve (EOO=4 km²; AOO=4 km²; 457 m a.s.l.). Too little is known about the location, LIFE STYLE: and threats of this taxon for a full assessment to be made. Identification of the species is also problematic; it is therefore listed as Data Deficient for Taxonomic reasons.

GLOBAL DISTRIBUTION: South Africa: Limpopo.

DISTRIBUTION IN SOUTH AFRICA: type locality only as Transvaal*.

LIFE STYLE: The species is known from the Savanna Biome.

CONSERVATION MEASURES: Unknown.

TAXONOMIC NOTES: Not revised. Known only from female, not illustrated.

GENUS *NEOSCONA* Simon, 1864

The genus *Neoscona* described by Simon (1864) is known from 116 species and 11 subspecies with a world-wide distribution. Seventeen species have been recorded from South Africa (World Spider Catalog 2020).

COMMON NAMES: Neoscona Hairy Field Spiders

TYPE SPECIES: *Neoscona arabesca* (Walckenaer, 1841)

MORPHOLOGY: Spiders of this genus are small to medium in size. The females are usually larger than the males. The colour varies from cream to brown to greyish black with a distinct abdominal pattern in many species allowing the spider to blend in with the environment when resting. Presence of longitudinal thoracic groove in female separates *Neoscona* from all members of the genus *Araneus*. Median ocular quadrangle forming a trapezium that is slightly longer than wide; anterior medians largest or subequal to the posterior medians; lateral eyes close and not situated on prominent tubercles, posterior laterals smallest; both rows of eyes recurved. In males coxa I ventrally provided with a hook on the distal rim; tibia II having macrosetae (spines) on prolateral surface. Abdomen may be oval, sub oval, triangular or sub-triangular in shape. Epigyne is a simple tongue like; scape completely fused to the base and provided with one or two pairs of lateral lobes; epigynal openings situated underneath of scape. Palpal patella of male provided with two strong, curved and long spines.

LIFE STYLE: Orb-webs are usually made at night and removed early in the morning. The spider rest on the vegetation. In some species distinct retreats are made close to the web. The spiders are very commonly found in grassland and savanna in low vegetation (Dippenaar-Schoeman & Haddad 2014); Dippenaar-Schoeman 2014);

TAXONOMY: The African species was revised by Grasshoff (1986).

Orb-web Photo Allen Jones

Neoscona subfusca Photo Peter Webb

Neoscona moreli orb-web Photo Allen Jones

Neoscona rufipalpis Photo Peter Webb

Neoscona alberti (Strand, 1913)

COMMON NAME: Albert's Neoscona Orb-Web Spider

CONSERVATION STATUS: LC

NATIONAL RATIONALE: An African endemic described by Strand (1913) from the Democratic Republic of the Congo as *Aranea alberti*. It has been sampled from five African countries and is possibly under collected, suspected to occur in more countries in-between. In South Africa, the species is known from two provinces (EOO=24 260 km²; AOO=16 km²; 552-2826 m a.s.l.). Due to its wide geographical range, the species is listed as being of Least Concern.

GLOBAL DISTRIBUTION: Democratic Republic of the Congo, Kenya, Rwanda, Zimbabwe and South Africa.

DISTRIBUTION IN SOUTH AFRICA: **Eastern Cape:** Grahamstown (-33.30, 26.52); Addo Elephant National Park (-33.32, 25.72). **KwaZulu-Natal:** Giant's Castle Nature Reserve (-29.23, 29.48) (NM); Drakensberg (Injasuti) (-29,18, 29.42) (NM).

LIFE STYLE: An orb-web species that builds orb-webs in vegetation at night, removing the webs early in the morning. Known from the Grassland and Thicket biomes (Haddad et al. 2013). The orb-web of the specimen from Grahamstown was made in *Spartina* grass (Grasshoff 1986).

CONSERVATION MEASURES: Protected in the Addo Elephant National Park (Dippenaar-Schoeman et al. 2020) and Giant's Castle Nature Reserve. There are no known threats to the species.

After Grasshoff (1986)

Neoscona alberti female from Addo NP

Neoscona alberti female ventral view Photo P. Webb

Neoscona angulatula (Schenkel, 1937)

COMMON NAME: Neoscona Orb-Web Spider

CONSERVATION STATUS: LC

NATIONAL RATIONALE: An African endemic described by Schenkel (1937) from Madagascar as *Araneus angulatulus*. The species has been recorded from five African countries. It is not very common in South Africa, and has been recorded only from KwaZulu-Natal within two protected areas. Due to its wide global geographical range, the species is listed as being of Least Concern.

GLOBAL DISTRIBUTION: Aldabra and Assumption, Kenya, Madagascar, Seychelles. New record: South Africa.

DISTRIBUTION IN SOUTH AFRICA: KwaZulu-Natal: Mkuzi Game Reserve (-27.63, 32.25); Ophathe Game Reserve (-28.52, 31.66).

LIFE STYLE: An orb-web species which builds orb-webs at night in vegetation, known from the Savanna Biome (Foord et al. 2011).

CONSERVATION MEASURES: Protected in two reserves: Mkuzi Game Reserve and Ophathe Game Reserve (Haddad & Dippenaar-Schoeman 2015). There are no known threats to the species.

TAXONOMIC NOTES: Revised by Grasshoff (1986). Known from both sexes.

After Grasshoff (1986)

Neoscona angulatula Photo Peter Webb

Neoscona blondeli (Simon, 1885)

COMMON NAME: Blondel's Neoscona Orb-Web Spider

CONSERVATION STATUS: LC

NATIONAL RATIONALE: An African endemic described by Simon (1885) from Liberia and known throughout Africa. The species is distributed widely in South Africa and has been recorded from all the provinces (EOO=1 071 783 km²; AOO=416 km²; 1-2 826 m a.s.l.). There are no significant threats to the species. Due to its wide geographical range, the species is listed as being of Least Concern.

GLOBAL DISTRIBUTION: Widespread throughout Africa. Sampled from Swaziland, Botswana and South Africa.

DISTRIBUTION IN SOUTH AFRICA: **Eastern Cape:** Alexandria (-33.65, 26.4); Cwebe Nature Reserve (-32.28, 28.9); Jeffrey's Bay (-34.06, 24.91); Kwandwe Private Game Reserve (-33.09, 26.57); Mkambati Nature Reserve (31.32, 29.97); Addo Elephant National Park (-33.32, 25.72); Kei River Mouth (-32.68, 28.37); Lusikisiki (-31.37, 29.57); Port St. Johns Umngazi Mouth (-31.63, 29.53); Qachas Nek (-30.12, 28.68). **Free State:** Bloemfontein (-29.11, 26.22); Bloemfontein (Farm Deelfontein) (-30.98, 23.81); Erfenis Dam Nature Reserve (-28.5, 26.8); Ficksburg (-28.86, 27.86); Mpetsane Conservation Estate (-28.8, 27.65); Wepener (-29.73, 27.03). **Gauteng:** Hekpoort (-25.9, 27.61); Melville Koppies (-26.17, 27.99); Poortview, Roodepoort (-26.15, 27.89); Pretoria/Tshwane following localities: Villieria (-25.71, 28.23), Wonderboom (-25.68, 28.2), Rietondale Research Station (-25.73, 28.23); Randburg (-26.07, 27.92); Roodeplaatdam Nature Reserve (-25.64, 28.36); Van Riebeeck Nature Reserve (-25.85, 28.16); Ezemvelo Nature Reserve (-25.8, 28.77); Irene Gem Village Field (-25.85, 28.16). **KwaZulu-Natal:** Amanzimtoti (-30.04, 30.88); Cathedral Peak (-28.94, 29.19); Dukuduku Forest Station (-28.37, 32.23); Empangeni (-28.72, 31.88); Giant's Cup Wilderness Reserve (Farm Goschen) (-29.97, 29.46); iSimangaliso Wetland Park: False Bay Park (-27.92, 32.27), Hell's Gate (-28, 32.48), Kosi Bay Nature Reserve (-26.93, 32.87), Lake Sibaya (-27.35, 32.7), Sodwana Bay National Park (-27.4, 32.76), St. Lucia (-28.36, 32.41), Mapelane Nature Reserve (-28.39, 32.42), Mkuzi Game Reserve (-27.63, 32.25); Hillcrest (-29.77, 30.72); Hluhluwe (-28.02, 32.28); Illovo Beach (-30.12, 30.85); Jozini (-27.42, 32.07); Margate (-30.85, 30.36); Mount Edgecombe (-29.68, 31.03); Mtubatuba (-28.4, 32.18); Ndumo Game Reserve (-26.87, 32.24); Ngome State Forest (-27.78, 31.45); Oribi Gorge Nature Reserve (-30.71, 30.26); Port Edward (-31.04, 30.21); Pietermaritzburg (-29.6, 30.38); Pongola (Farm Vergeval) (-27.35, 31.61); Richards Bay (15 km N)

Tibia 1-11.

After Grasshoff (1986)

Neoscona blondeli female of Wakkerstroom Photo P. Webb

Neoscona blondeli female from Irene Photo Peter Webb

Neoscona blondeli (continued)

Tembe Elephant Park (-26.94, 32.47); Umfolozi Nature Reserve (-28.3, 31.76); Umgeni River (-29.26, 30.32); Umkomaas (-30.2, 30.8); Vryheid Nature Reserve (-27.75, 30.79). **Limpopo:** Alma (-24.49, 28.07); Blouberg Nature Reserve (-22.99, 29.04); Dendron (Farm Amsterdam) (-23.37, 29.32); Lajuma Mountain Retreat (-23.03, 29.45); Lekgalameetsi Nature Reserve (-23.82, 30.16); Little Leigh (-22.95, 29.87); Nylstroom/ Modimolle (-24.69, 28.4); Makalali Nature Reserve (-24.34, 30.93); Nylsvley Nature Reserve (-24.65, 28.67); Pafuri Camp (-22.42, 30.91); Polokwane Nature Reserve (-23.9, 29.47); Potgietersrus/ Mokopane (-24.17, 29.00); Swadini Nature Reserve (-24.34, 30.93); Tshulu (Venda) (-22.58, 30.81); Springbok Flats: Tuinplaas (-24.9, 28.73); Tzaneen (-23.82, 30.16); Vaalwater (-24.29, 28.11). **Mpumalanga:** Bourke's Luck (-25.09, 30.46); Brondal (-25.35, 30.84); Dullstroom (-25.42, 30.1); Kruger National Park (Skukuza) (-25.00, 31.97); Lydenburg (-25.09, 30.46); Middelburg (-25.76, 29.46); Nelspruit (-25.47, 30.96); Noordkaap (-25.66, 31.07); Ohrigstad (-24.74, 30.58); Pilgrims Rest (-24.89, 30.75). **North West:** Barberspan (-26.62, 25.58); Borakalalo Game Reserve (-25.14, 27.82); Brits (-25.62, 27.77); Buffelspoort Research Station (-25.62, 27.77); Swartruggens (Farm Olivenkloof) (-25.54, 26.52); Pilanesberg Nature Reserve (-25.25, 27.08); Rustenburg Nature Reserve (-25.72, 27.18). **Northern Cape:** Hope-town (Farm Suffolk) (-29.58, 24.24); Tswalu Game Reserve (-27.3, 22.44). **Western Cape:** Brackenfeld Nature Reserve (-33.9, 18.72); Durbanville (-33.83, 18.66); Grootvadersbos (-26.5, 28.36); Karoo National Park (-32.28, 22.46); Stellenbosch (-33.93, 18.85); Bontebok National Park (-34.07, 20.45); Robben Island (-33.8, 18.35).

LIFE STYLE: A very common orb-web species, which builds webs in vegetation at night and removes them early in the morning. Sampled from all the floral biomes except the Desert and Succulent Karoo biomes (Foord et al. 2011; Haddad et al. 2013). Also found in crops such as avocado, cotton, pecans, pistachio, tomatoes and vineyards (Dippenaar-Schoeman et al. 2013).

CONSERVATION MEASURES: There are no known threats to the species. Protected in >20 protected areas such as the Addo Elephant National Park (Dippenaar-Schoeman et al. 2020); Karoo National Park (Dippenaar-Schoeman et al. 1999); Mkambati Nature Reserve (Dippenaar-Schoeman et al. 2011); Makalali NR (Whitmore et al. 2001); Ndumo Game Reserve (Haddad et al. 2006); Polokwane NR (Dippenaar et al. 2008) Tembe Elephant Park (Haddad et al. 2009).

TAXONOMIC NOTES: Revised by Grasshoff (1986). Known from both sexes.

Neoscona blondeli female from Alberts Falls
Photo J.van Zyl

Neoscona blondeli immature female from Kloof
Photo P. Webb

Neoscona blondeli Woodbush
Photo P. Webb

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